

HIMALAYAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

A bi-annual peer reviewed journal

Published by
Harkamaya College of Education
Samdur, Tadong Gangtok, Sikkim-737102

Managed by
RHENOCK EDUCATION SOCIETY
Fiveways, Deorali, Gangtok, Sikkim-737102
www.hcesikkim.org/www.res.ac.in

HIMALAYAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

(ISSN : 2231-6639)

Vol-6 Issue No.2 October, 2016

A bi - annual peer reviewed journal

Published by

**Harkamaya College of Education
Samdur, Gangtok**

Managed by :

RHENOCK EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY

**Fiveways, Deorali, Sikkim - 737102
www.hcesikkim.org / www.res.ac.in**

HARKAMAYACOLLEGE OF EDUCATION
(A Constituent College of Rhenock Educational Society)

The Harkamaya College of Education a constituent college of Rhenock Educational Society is situated at Samdur, P.O. Tadong in the district of East Sikkim on the roadside of N.H.10 (previously N.H. 31 A) which runs from Siliguri to Gangtok. An eminent educationist and administrator, Dr. H.P. Chhetri is its Director. Nathula trade center, Tsongo Lake, Gurudomgmar lake, Baba Mandir, Yungthang, Pelling and the picturesque Kanchenjunga are the beautiful scenic tourist places. Most importantly, from this year the second route to Kailash-Mansarovar Yatra through Nathula Pass is also going to open. Students from Assam, Bihar, Bengal, U.P, and North Eastern states are enrolled as student teachers. Students of Bhutan and Nepal are also reading in this institution. The college is permanently recognised by NCTE since 2003-04 and Sikkim University since 2013-14; and also accredited by NAAC.

The mission and vision of the college are: Producing intellectual, enlightened, cultivated and resourceful teachers having sound knowledge and solid thought, teachers with commitment and devotion, effective leadership, good social human beings, true researchers and innovators, professionally skilled in teaching, good social workers, men with vision of integrity, tendency for enculturation of cultural heritage and ready workers for community development activities and above all developing academic pursuits through research and innovation.

HIMALAYAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

(ISSN No. 2231-6639)

PATRON

*Dr. H.P.CHETTRI. M.A. (Soc.) Meerut;Ph.D (Sociology) NBU
Director, Harkamaya College of Education*

EDITORIAL ADVISORY BOARD

*Dr. Basanti Dey Chakraborty
Associate Professor
Childhood Education
New Jersey City University
Jersey City, N.J 07305, USA*

*Dr. D. Mukhopadhyay
Professor
Department of Education
N.S.B. University, Kolkata
West Bengal*

*Dr. Pranati Panda
Professor of Education
NUEPA, New Delhi*

*Prof. G.C. Nanda
Professor of Education
Ravenshaw University
Cuttack, Odisha*

*Prof. (Dr.) S.M.Pani
Principal cum Professor (Retd.)
Upendra Bhawan, Chandini Chowk
Cuttack -753002*

*Prof. Mita Banerjee
Vice Chancellor Early
W.B. Teacher Training University
Ballygaunge, Kolkata.*

*Dr. S.C. Panda
Professor and Principal (Retd.)
Consultant, NIOS,
New Delhi*

*Dr. B.K.Swain
Professor & Head
P.G. Dept. of Sociology
RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur*

*Prof. (Dr). N. Pradhan
Principal
RIE, Bhopal*

*Prof. D. Harichandan
Professor & Director
IDOL, University of Bombay
Mumbai*

HIMALAYAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

(ISSN . 2231-6639)

Volume 6, Issue No. 2, October, 2016

Editor in Chief

Prof (Dr) P.L. Mohapatra

Associate Editors

Dr. P. K. Mishra

Principal

D.S. College

Gangtok

Dr. H.P. Mishra

Principal

Sagardighi Teachers' Training College

Murshidabad, W.B

Dr. S.S Mahapatra

Associate Professor

Deptt. of Commerce

Sikkim University, Gangtok

Dr. S.K.Padhi

Asst. Professor

GGD Central University

Bilashpur (C.G)

Dr. Laxmidhar Behera

Asso. Professor in Education

RIE, Bhubanaswar

Dr. Sarat Kumar Rout

Asst. Professor in Education

Ravenshaw University, Cuttack

Dr. O.P.Gadde

Asst. Professor

Deptt. of Pol.Science

Sikkim University, Gangtok

711202

Dr. Abhijit Guha

Associate Professor in Education

Ramakrishna Mission Shikshanmandira

Belur Math, Howrah, West Bengal-

Dr. Mitanjali Sahoo

Asst. Professor In Education

Department of Education

Central University of Bihar

Gaya Campus, Bihar - 823001

Ms. Keekee Fern Cargay

Asst. Professor

Harkamaya College of Education

Gangtok.

Ms. Magdolyn Karthak

Asst. Professor

Harkamaya College of Education

Gangtok

Ms. Ranita Chakraborty

Asst. Professor

Harkamaya College of Education

Gangtok

From the Editors' Desk

In the present learning society, it is needed that everyone must learn in a variety of educational situations and ideally, everyone should become alternately a learner and a teacher. Importance of lifelong learning is the clarion call of today. If knowledge, skill and learning abilities are not renewed, it would be difficult to adapt to the new environment. The necessity of continuous learning by teacher has been stressed from the beginning. Gurudev Rabindranath Tagore in his deliberation had stressed upon the continuous learning by the teacher by saying that teacher having no living traffic with his knowledge, can only load their minds, but cannot quicken them. The concept of learning community generally covers teachers and students and in a wider context, it also covers the parents and the community. Recent stress on the knowledge society has made nations to review and re-organise their capacities for accessing and benefitting for shaping the nation commensurate with the social change. High quality learning communities have teachers who are skilled in transforming the classrooms and diversifying learning sites. In such classrooms, effective teachers can be successful. A teacher becomes effective by effective functioning in the class to transform the students to pragmatic approaches, catering to the fast changing social order. For this the teacher has to keep himself abreast with the knowledge exposure and dynamism so that he can be one or two steps ahead of his knowledgeable students. This he can achieve only through constant research and approaches to innovation. Such attempts of some notable teachers have found place in this issue of our journal. Articles from different streams like sociology, geography, political science and education have been reviewed and contented in this issue. There has been a general attempt to sensitise the learning community in different critical issues of the present society. It is expected that all would be benefitted out of these published articles and would develop awareness to react to such situations. Any constructive suggestion for qualitative improvement in the standard of the publication would very highly be appreciated.

BOARD OF EDITORS

Contents

Sl. No.	Topic Name	Page No.
1.	Achievement Motivation and Study Habits influencing Academic Achievement of Secondary School Children of Working and Non working Mothers <i style="text-align: right;">Dr. Debasmita Das</i>	1-17
2.	Gender Deconstruction as a Tool for Ending Sexual Violence Against Women <i style="text-align: right;">Dr. Chongtick Lachungpa</i>	18-29
3.	Perception of Secondary School Teachers for Generating Learning Friendly Classroom Environment <i style="text-align: right;">Dr. Mitanjali Sahoo</i>	30-40
4.	Application of Quantitative Techniques for Road Network Connectivity Analysis in Dakshin Dinajpur District of West Bengal <i style="text-align: right;">Dr. Pradip Chouhan</i>	41-57
5.	Role of Neo humanist School in Moral Development of Children at Primary Level- A Case Study <i style="text-align: right;">Mrs. Sunandita Bhowmik Dr. Ramakanta Mohalik</i>	58-67
6.	An Interactional Study of Academic Anxiety in Relation to Gender and School Type among Secondary School Students <i style="text-align: right;">Magdolyn Karthak</i>	68-81
7.	The Attitude towards School among the Students of West Bengal <i style="text-align: right;">Sohel Rana Sarkar Dr. Abhijit Guha</i>	82-92
8.	Anxiety in Women Teachers and its Impact on Adjustment of their Own Children <i style="text-align: right;">Pratistha Kumari</i>	93-111
9.	Book Review <i style="text-align: right;">Dr. Pragyant Mohanty</i>	112-114

Achievement Motivation and Study Habits influencing Academic Achievement of Secondary School Children of Working and Non-working Mothers

Dr. Debasmita Das*

Abstract

The study was intended to the study of interrelationship between the achievement motivation, study habit and academic achievement of children of working and non-working women. The study was conducted over a sample of 400 Class X of secondary schools of Balasore district. Purposive sampling procedure was adopted. The following tools Achievement Motivation Inventory of Mehta (1969) for measuring Achievement Motivation., Anand's Study Habit Inventory for measuring study habits, SES scale of Nayak (2005) also for selection of the sample and Personal Data Blank of students to study working and non-working mothers of the sample. The findings of the study were; there was no significant difference in achievement motivation in case of the respondents of working and non working mothers. But significant difference existed in case of boys and girls of working mothers, Gender difference in study habit scores showed non-significant difference. Hence, it was concluded that study habit wise, the boys and girls do not have any difference. The academic achievement of working and non-working mothers' children showed significant difference in case of boys only; significant relationship existed between achievement motivation, study habit and academic achievement in both the cases of working and non working mothers' children

Key words: Study habit, n-Achievement, Academic achievement, Purposive Sampling

Introduction

The term n-achievement or need achievement in place of achievement motivation was introduced by Murray (1938). According to him need-achievement means to accomplish something difficult or to master, manipulate or organize physical objects, human beings or ideas and to do this as rapidly and as independently as possible.

Achievement Motivation is based on affective arousal theory of McClelland (1958). This model of motivation is primarily based upon the concept of associative tendencies. Accordingly to the proponents of society, two affective status of the organism serve as important motivators. One of them is negative i.e. fear and anxiety and the other is positive; hope of success or anticipation of rewards. Both of these are learned or conditioned reactions.

*C/o-Dr. Manorama Das, M.B.S.Jail Road, Azimabad, Balasore, Odisha, 756001

will satisfy their needs through different means, and are driven to succeed for varying reasons both

*C/o-Dr. Manorama Das, M.B.S.Jail Road, Azimabad, Balasore, Odisha, 756001

internal and external.

Achievement motivation is the attitude to achieve rather than the achievements themselves. It can be considered as extended person – intrinsic motivation because its reinforcement is delayed. It arises from an interaction within the person. Achievement motivation is “a pattern of planning of actions and of feelings connected with striving to achieve some internalized standard of excellence, as contrasted for example, will power or friendship (Vidler, 1977).

Achievement motivation otherwise known as need for achievement can be defined as a motive to strive for success.

Concept of Study Habit

Study habits are learning tendencies that enable students to work privately. Azikiwe (1998) described the study habit as “the adopted way and manner a student plans his private readings after classroom learning so as to attain mastery of the subject”. According to her, “good study habits are good assets to learners because the habits assist students to attain mastery in areas of specialisation and consequent excellent performance, while opposite constitute constraints to learning and achievement leading to failure”.

Study habits are the habits especially related to the behaviour of an individual pertaining to the domain of his working at studies. How an individual conducts himself at his studies is adjudged from his study habits. Styles of studying are known as study habits. The practicing modus operandi of a student for making his studies is essentially contained in his study habits.

In the process of learning, habitual ways of exercising and practicing their abilities for learning are considered as study habits of learners. The pattern of behaviour adopted by students in the pursuit of their studies is considered under the caption of 'study habits'.

An investigation to study habits of students makes a study of their placement at studies. Study habits reveal student's personality in action at their studies. Learner's learning character is characterized by his study habits. The assessment of study habits of school students, college students, teachers, working adults needs to be different.

Study habits are intended to elicit and guide one's cognitive processes during learning. Self-directed learners possess appropriate study habits and use them at the appropriate study hours and use them at the appropriate times and places during learning. When the learner's goal is solely good retention performance, then study habits that promote the selecting process are important. When the learner's

goal is transfer performance, than the study habits should be used that engage selecting, and integrating process.

Role of Family in Children's Academic Achievement

The first exposure of the child is the family. Child learns the first lesson of humanity between the kisses of the mother and lap of father. Mother is the most important intermediary in the process of socialization, education and development of the child. child's psychological make-up, value pattern and achievement largely depends upon the interaction of the mother and the child. It is the early home environment that determine the personality of the child. A number of research studies (Trivedi, 1987) show very significant relationship between family environment and the development process of the child. even after the beginning of the schooling, home continues its powerful influence to determine the nature of the child's response to school. It acts as motivational process. It provides an environment that affect attitude, personality and achievement of the child.

It is the kind of early parent child interaction in the home that determine whether a child would develop into a dependent or independent ascendant or submissive, co-operative or competitive person. Early mother child relationship is essential for the growth of personality of the child. Mental development of the child depends to a great extent on how mothers handle their children. Mother is that pivot around which the life of child revolve and loss of mother has its paralyzing effect on mental functioning, development of self and personality. Child deprived of mother's presence and the warmth of her lap during the early childhood lacks those skills which are required to master the cognitive experiences of today's school, because of narrow perceptual field available for exploration of the maternal skills in guiding him to seek out the wonder and beauty of the natural world, Zaidi (1986). Douglas (1965) stated that role of mother involves more than a succession of separate acts of child rearing patterns. The quality and character of a mother as an individual has an important bearing on her performance as mother. That is why so much of importance is given to the educational empowerment and anticipation of women, for only a healthy and educated mother can train healthier and positive sides of life. It is that attitude and the personality of the mother which determine the manner in which she administers each and every aspect of child care.

Mother and child together build-up a very soft and intimate relation. Mother's role during adolescence is of great importance. This is the age when the child lays the foundation for adult life, inculcation of right values and belief. As a transition age in the process of human development, it is

the span of year during which boys and girls move from childhood to adulthood mentally, emotionally, socially and physically. It is the time of rapid physiological and psychological changes, of intensive readjustment to the family, school, work and social life and of preparation for adult's role. This is very crucial not only for adolescent, but also for the parents, especially for the mother who consider child as one of her own part, her own privilege possession. At this stage she has to play the role of a guide and become a role model to facilitate individualization of adolescent. Psychoanalytical thinkers and learning theorists have given considerable evidences regarding the crucial importance of the cognitive development. But working mothers who engage in a work life, aside from their duties as child are provider, are not in a position to discharge their duties. Working mothers face a lot of difficulties in maintaining a healthy work life.

Working Mothers and its Impact on Children

In the past two decades, there has been a dramatic increase in the number of working women, especially among married women lining with their spouses and whose children have reached school age. It is estimated that at present one third of these married women are employed outside the home and it is expected that this movement of mothers from the home into the labour market will continue for at least the next decade, Fankel (2012). The effects of maternal employment on family structure as well as on child development and function have been the focus of an increasing number of research studies. Among the areas studied have been the effects of maternal employment on school achievement.

Child rearing process and practices in families of working and non-working mothers were investigated in 1930-1940s. It was observed that child rearing practices are not related to work status. When mothers' motivations and education are concerned along with work status, associations with child rearing appear.

Mothers who prefer to work but out of a sense of duty do not report the most problems in child rearing. Children are under firmer control and are given more responsibilities by working mothers than by non-working mothers. This difference does not exist between working and non-working college – trained mothers. College trained mothers tend to compensate for mother's employment away from home by more planned activities with the children (Yarrow, Scott, Leuwad Heinic, 1962).

Rationale of the study

The concern for the excellence in Education is as old as the man himself. The central focus of all

formal educational effort is on academic achievement of the learners. Quality of performance has become the key factor for personal progress. A growing concern is developing in the parents for academic excellence of their children. But owing to modern civilization and parents' engagement for earning more money, maximum parents are interested in employment. These makes the women preferring work at home and serve in the organization. Therefore, the mothers find no time to cater to the needs and requirements of their children and children are deprived of parental involvement in their studies as well as their emotional and social development. In this connection, the following question are arise.

- What are the factors responsible for high academic achievement? Are parents having any role to play ?
- Is home factor an essential condition for this?
- What is the impact of working and non-working mothers on the academic achievement of the Children?
- Are the working and non-working status of mothers responsible in cognitive and non-cognitive development of their children?

Answers to the above questions let the investigator to investigate and to show the comparative effectiveness of working and non-working status of mothers and its impact upon the non-cognitive correlates to academic achievement. The major findings of the reviews also purport the same viewpoint that academic achievement is a function of both cognitive and non-cognitive variables.

But different research studies have been conducted to assess the contributions different non-cognitive and cognitive variables in proportion variance in different magnitude. Taking cognizance of the present scenario of high premium put on non-cognitive attributes, women being engaged in job are far away from their children's career building because of working conditions. This is due to the reasons that working women have little contribution for shaping the destiny of their children. Hence this has been an intervening variable for the study. The present study was a sincere attempt of the investigator to determine in what proportion and direction achievement motivation and study habits are accountable to the scholastic achievement of the sample of working and non-working mothers.

On the basis of the arguments stated above the study was entitled as “Achievement Motivation and Study Habits influencing Academic Achievement of Secondary School Children of Working and Non-working Mothers”.

Objectives of the study

- To study the nature and sex differences in achievement motivation, study habit and academic achievement of adolescents of working and non-working mothers.
- To study the inter-relationship among achievement motivation, study habit and academic achievement of adolescents group wise and totally of the children of working and non-working mothers.
- To study the interaction effect of two independent variables together towards academic achievement in each case of students of working and non-working mothers.
- To study the joint and relative contribution of achievement motivation, study habits towards academic achievement of adolescents of working and nonworking mothers by deriving a multiple regression equation for predicting them.

Formulation of Hypotheses

Ho₁ : There is no significant differences in the achievement motivation of boys and girls of working and non-working mothers.

Ho₂ : There is no significant difference in the study habits of boys and girls of working and non-working mothers.

Ho₃ : There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of boys and girls of working and non-working mothers.

Ho₄ : There is no significant relationship between achievement motivation, study habits and academic achievement of boys and girls of working and non working mothers.

Ho₅ : There is no significant differences in the academic achievement of boys and girls due to high, average and low levels of achievement motivation.

Ho₆ : There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of boys and girls due to high, average and low degree of study habits adopted by them.

Ho₇ : There is no significant interaction effect of high, average and low levels of achievement motivation and study habit scores on the academic achievement of the adolescents in case of the respondents of working mothers.

Ho₈ : There is no significant interaction effect of high average and low levels of achievement motivation and study habit scores on the academic achievement of the adolescents in case of non-working mothers.

Ho₉ : Academic achievement of the adolescents of the working and non-working mothers cannot be significantly predicted with the help of scores of the two predicting variables of achievement motivation and study habit.

Operational Definitions of the Terms Used

Achievement Motivation here refers to the tendency to strive for success in competition against some standard of excellence as a multidimensional attribute which are indicated by persistence, personal responsibility, realistic goal orientation, achievement satisfaction and recognition behaviour. It has been measured as per the scale developed by Mehta (1967) which is a Thematic Apperception Test (TAT).

Study Habit – The dictionary meaning of study habit is the settled tendency of practice and thought to acquire knowledge and information from the books. The components of the study habits Inventory here were conceptualized along the lines of the inventory developed and standardized by Anand (1990). The inventory measured the dimensions of self study, seriousness in study, comprehension and hard work.

Academic Achievement refers to the level of achievement in various subjects as indicated by marks or grade points in the final board examination of Class X. This was considered as the criterion measure of the study. Working and non-working mothers referred to the mothers in jobs and mothers as housewives not engaged in any type of job which compel them to stay outside the homes.

Significance of the Study

The importance of the present study could hardly be over emphasized. Though life success is not synonymous with school success, success in the school is the yardstick for majority of children for their future life. A need was felt therefore, to explore this domain empirically and specify the role of achievement motivation, study habit on academic achievement. These affective variables have recently been identified as influential factors. Such a study was assumed to analyse the inner forces underlying the achievement of high school students along with providing a framework for the conceptualization of an academic motivation theory.

Besides this, the findings can be of great practical value as they may help in reconstructing the society in the present form of social order. Because it may help parents in creating favourable conditions for scholastic growth of students.

The study was also justified for another reason. The mothers at present are inclined for jobs and dual

earning in the family has been a regular feature. Therefore, whether the working status of the mothers would help in enhancement of the academic programme is another interaction of this study. Whether the family environment because of working mothers is conducive for growth and development of the adolescents need the attention at present. In that context, the study has importance.

Delimitations of the Study

The study was confined to the schools located under Balasore Municipality. As per the provisions made by Government, there was no private Odia medium high schools. The CBSE/ ICSE schools were also included in the study to level the socio-economic status.

Method of Study

The Design

The study design was a causal comparative study. It was also an ex-post-facto study for the study habit and achievement motivation were studied as they were.

The Sample

A purposive sample pool of 400 students studying in 10 secondary schools of different interventions like only Boys, only Girls and co-ed schools was selected for the study. In order to make the sample homogenous first of all a chart was drawn under the heads age, sex and type of institution along with role strength. Out of 400 students selected as sample for the study, care was taken to select the students of same SES and intelligence level for which an intelligence test was administered and the educational, occupational and income status score of the parents was measured and fixed within the score range of 15-17 (SES Scale of Nayak, 2005). Thus, the sample was reduced to 300, Boys-146 and Girls-154, working mothers-130, Non working mothers-170, Boys of working mothers-60, Girls of working mothers-70, Boys of non-working mothers-86, Girls of nonworking mothers-84.

Tools Used

The following tools were used in the study: Achievement Motivation Inventory of Mehta (1969) for measuring Achievement Motivation, Anand's Study Habit Inventory for measuring study habits; SES scale of Nayak (2005), A Personal Data Bank to study working and non-working mothers of the sample.

Techniques of Analysis

The techniques of data analysis include, t -ratio, for measuring test of significance between two contrasts, 'r' for relationship between the variables and multiple correlation as well as multiple co

efficient of Determination for prediction and ANOVA for Interaction study were used.

The Findings of the Study

1. Gender Differences in all the Variables

The present study being intended to find out the significant difference between boys and girls of working and non-working mothers could not be established as the '*t*' ratio was not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis could not be rejected. The result obtained revealed that irrespective of mothers' role perception, there is no influence of this on the level of achievement motivation of adolescent boys and girls. The gender differences in study habit scores were also calculated and it was observed that in none of the cases the '*t*' ratio was significant even though there were some differences in the study habits of boys of working mothers and girls of working mothers, girls of working mothers and girls of non-working mothers. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in study habits of adolescents of working and non-working mothers could not be rejected. Rai (2010) did not observe any difference in study habits of boys and girls. The present study therefore may be accepted as appropriate as many studies showed no significant difference in study habits.

In order to find out significance of differences in academic achievement of boys and girls of working and non-working mothers the '*t*' ratio was calculated in each contrast. It was concluded that academic achievement wise there was no difference in the boys and girls, but there was significant difference in total students of working mothers and non-working mothers. The '*t*' ratio was also significant in case of boys of working mothers and boys of non-working mothers. Even though the mean differences existed in between boys and girls of working and non-working mothers, the same were not significant. Hence, the null hypothesis formulated as, there is no significant difference in academic achievement of respondents of working and non-working mothers was rejected, yet subsample wise that difference could not be established. Only in case of boys of working and non-working mothers, it showed significant difference.

Studies of Shaw (2011), Kaur et al. (2009) showed significant differences in academic achievement in case of boys and girls of working and non-working mothers. Khanna (2011) in a study attributed this difference due to higher level of emotional intelligence in case of non-working women Akhni et al. (1999) showed that material employment had no interfering effect on achievement. Studies of Chaturvedi (1996) and Guha et al. (1995) revealed that maternal role perception was related to

achievement. They further substantiated that the adolescents of professional and non-professional mothers differed in material role perception and achievement.

2. Inter-relationship Study

One of the objectives of the study was to assess the inter-relationship among achievement motivation, study habit and academic achievement of adolescents of working and non-working mothers. Therefore, attempts were made to compute the co-efficient of correlation between the variables separately and totally. All the values were tested for significance and interpretation was made as per the results. It was observed that the relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement, study habit and academic achievement of children of working mothers was 0.445, and 0.332 respectively, whereas the same in case of non working mothers' children were 0.889 and 0.528 respectively. All were highly significant at 0.01 level. Further, it was observed that the co-efficient of correlations between achievement motivation, study habit and academic achievement in all the three groups were highly significant (0.01 level of significance). This revealed that as the achievement motivation increases in the respondents, the study habit develops; the academic achievement also gets increased. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated earlier that there is no significant relationship in achievement motivation and academic achievement were rejected. The results showing significant positive relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement seemed to be self evident as students who wanted to perform better and strive for success in competition are most likely to obtain high marks in their school examinations. On the contrary, those who lack persistence are scared of competitions and do not want to achieve high are likely to get low marks in examinations.

Further, when the nature of achievement motive was considered, the result obtained in the present study was considered appropriate. Because studies have earlier shown that those high on achievement motive set moderately difficult goals for themselves, get highly interested in concrete feedback, assume personal responsibility and generally show more initiative and explanatory behaviour (McClelland & Winter, 1969), further oriented and action minded (Weiner, 1970).

All these characteristics evinced a formidable combination of practical, venturesome and determined personality which can achieve brilliant results in the sphere of academics. A student possessing these characteristics would certainly learn rigorously and ultimately prove to be a better examination achiever. This was evinced from the studies of Nayak (2005), Mishra (2007) and Chhetri (2012). In

these studies, individuals high on achievement motive were seen as confident of success. The zero-order correlations between study habit and academic achievement of the respondents of working and non-working mothers were highly significant. This revealed the fact that the students with high achievement motive being realistic in their approaches, enthusiastic and persistent must have worked hard for more marks. Hence they have developed good study habits. The findings were in conformity with earlier researches of Jagannathan (1985), Gupta (1987), Mohanty (1999), and Sahoo (2001), Kumar and Mohapatra (2008), Chhetri (2009).

3. Interaction Analysis of the two Predicting Variables on Academic Achievement

Another objective of the study was to analyse the interaction effect of both achievement motivation and study habit taken together on academic achievement in case of both the children of working and non-working mothers. This was done in an ANOVA. It was revealed that the main effect of achievement motivation on academic achievement was highly significant, where as non-significant effect of study habit was observed. But the interaction effect of both achievement motivation and study habit on academic achievement was again found to be significant. Both the predicting variables were split into three distinct groups of high, average and low. Thus a 2×2 factorial design was employed for the analysis with the achievement scores inserted into the cells and the data were then computerized. The final results along with the sum of squares, 'F' values and their significance levels were presented in a table for the respondents of working mothers.

The main effect of achievement motive showing an 'F' value of (202.409) in case of working mother's children was very high. This gave an added confidence to the researcher in interpreting that high, average and low achievement motive groups of adolescents of working mothers averaged over 3 levels of study habit differ significantly from each other. It meant that the achievement marks of the respondents were dependent upon the three levels of achievement motivation. Therefore, the hypothesis (H05) of no significant difference in the academic achievement of high, average and low levels of achievement motivation scores was rejected.

The effect of interaction between achievement motivation and study habit scores for the respondents of working mothers was also found to be significant as the 'F' value was 2.838 which has a significance value ($p=.027$). As the interaction effect was significant, it was revealed that the difference between the means of high, average, low levels of achievement motive along with the same level of study habits had effected significant effect on academic achievement. On the contrary it

may be concluded that the difference between high, average and low level of achievement of the respondents of working mothers were dependent upon the high, average and low levels of study habit scores. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H07) formulated earlier that “there is no significant interaction effect of high, average and low levels of achievement motivation and study habit scores on the academic achievement scores of the adolescents stands rejected.

In case of non-working mothers, the ANOVA was also calculated. The results revealed that the main effect of achievement motivation on academic achievement of respondents of non-working mothers was highly significant, the F value being 239.659. This gave an added confidence in interpreting that the mean academic achievement of high, average and low achievement motivation groups of students averaged over three levels of study habit differed significantly from each other. It meant that the marks in academic achievement are dependent on the differences or effect of achievement motive. Thus the hypothesis of no significant difference in the academic achievement of high, average and low levels of achievement scores of the respondents of non-working mothers also stands rejected.

The 'F' value for the main effect of study habit scores failed to reach the level of significance in case of the respondents of non-working mothers. This led to the conclusion that mean academic achievement scores for high, average and low groups on study habit do not differ significantly. It revealed that the academic achievement scores were independent of the differences in or the effect of study habit. Hence, the hypothesis stating no significant difference in the academic achievement of high, average and low levels of study habit groups was accepted. The same result was also obtained in case of the respondents of working mothers. The interaction effect between achievement motivation and study habit scores in case of the respondents of non-working mothers was not found to be significant for academic achievement as the F value was 0.518. The fact that the interaction was not significant, it indicated that the difference between the means of high, average and low levels of achievement motivation for study habit were not significantly different from the difference between the means of same levels of academic achievement. The conclusion was therefore drawn that the difference between High, Average and Low levels of study habit on the academic achievement scores were independent of the High, Average and Low levels of achievement motivation in case of the respondents of non-working mothers.

For this the co-efficient of multiple correlation was used to denote the strength of relationship

between the variables, the dependent variable of academic achievement and the independent variable of achievement motivation and study habit. This signified the relationship between the dependent variable and a combination of the two independent variables. To find out the measure of correlation between X1 (dependent variable) and the combined effects of X2 and X3, required designated formula was decided to be $R_{1.23}$ where the sub-script 1 stood for the academic achievement and subscripts 2 and 3 stood for achievement motivation and study habit.

The co-efficient of Multiple Determination was then found out to assess the contribution of the independent variables of Achievement Motivation and Study Habit towards Academic Achievement. It was observed that the same was found to be 0.818 in case of adolescents of working mothers, 0.792 in case of the adolescents of non-working mothers and 0.796 in case of the total sample. The results revealed that in case of the working mother's sample of respondents about 81.8 per cent was contributed towards academic achievement by the two independent variables, in case of non-working mothers' sample the same was 79.2 percent of proportion variance and in total sample, contribution of the independent variables to the criterion was 79.6 percent of the total variance. This showed that the contributions of highest amount.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were made depending upon the result.

1. One of the findings of the study was that there was no significant difference in achievement motivation in case of the respondents of working and non working mothers. But significant difference existed in case of boys and girls of working mothers. Therefore, conclusion was made that girls of working mothers look after the household work during their mothers' engagements in offices. Hence ,they develop intellectual achievement responsibility to achieve as well as they are afraid of mothers' stunting .Boys are left scot free as they are not supposed to do house hold work in a masculinity oriented world. So, in the absence of guardians they behave differently. Therefore, their achievement motivation is less.
2. Gender difference in study habit scores showed non –significant difference. Hence, it was concluded that study habit wise, the boys and girls do not have any difference. Therefore, it was concluded that in both the cases study hours were maintained.
3. The academic achievement of working and non-working mothers' children showed significant difference in case of boys only. Hence conclusion was made that there existed

significant difference because of non availability of mothers' at home and their indifference in guiding boys due to overwork and exhaustion in duty.

4. Significant relationship existing between achievement motivation, study habit and academic achievement in both the cases of working and non working mothers' children revealed that in both the cases all are concerned ,but the prediction values being higher in case of working mothers' children indicated impact of status , power and money in achievement. For this , it was concluded that private coaching be banned and equal opportunities be provided to all in classroom situations.

Educational Implications

From the present study it has been found that achievement has a perfect positive relationship with academic achievement. So in order to raise the academic achievement of the students it is essential to develop their achievement motivation .Therefore the situations in the home and in school should promote the need achievement of the pupil. In the context of the result in the present investigation the following recommendations have been made.

Emphasis on Intellectual Pursuit - Need achievement can be raised if the students develop their level of intelligence. Level of intelligence can be raised by encouraging the students to develop the problem solving ability, thinking, reasoning etc. by participation in different activities and studying the creative work of different persons. So far the development of achievement motivation among the students the intellectual development should be promoted. The school should organise different curricular and co curricular activities, like seminars, talks delivered by the intellectuals, debates, discussions etc. and should also promote students to gain correct and current information by studying the magazines, newspapers, journals, periodicals. It should encourage the students to study the creative writings of the eminent scholars. Not only the whole responsibility goes to the school and teachers for promoting achievement motivation but also the home, parents, elders, neighbours share a lot. Parents should also give the answers to each of the questions of their children with a great patience. They should maintain home atmosphere proper for the children's intellectual pursuit.

Affectionate Parental Behaviour - Achievement motivation is also influenced by the parental behaviour. Parents should be affectionate enough. They should listen and understand all the queries, problems and needs of their children and should try to solve them. They should encourage the children to meet each and every problem of their life. But they should not be over affectionate which

may spoil their children. Self actualization - Pupil of high self actualization are directed more by internal than external self-concept compared to that of those of low self actualization. Pupil of high self actualization are more flexible and less rigid and do not depend upon seeking approval from others, more capable of accepting themselves and others and the world around them. Permissiveness of parents - Parents should be permissive. They should encourage the children to know, to gain information by participating in different life situations. They should encourage them to be flexible, fearless and perceive the correct knowledge only after scientific and objective investigation. Development of level of aspiration - Pupils should have high level of aspiration. High level of aspiration is responsible for developing high need achievement. The teacher and the parents should set high goals before the students so that they should try to achieve them and they should develop the tendency to achieve more and more. But care must be taken that the goals should be set up by keeping an eye to the age, gender, intellectual standard and habitation variable or else it will have negative impact upon the children and may block their achievement. Reducing frustration reactions - Need achievement is also hampered by frustration. Frustration results from repeated failure in any activities. The process of blocking or thwarting needs causes frustration in human beings. If the children repeatedly fail in any activities they develop frustration reactions, which block their motive to achieve. So the children should be encouraged to develop their patience and to continue the activity until the success is achieved.

Removal of Prejudices and Biases - Conservative attitudes, prejudices attached to different situations and Objects are responsible in reducing the achievement motivation. The attitude of the people attached with the resistance of girls education, caste system, child marriages, preconceived ideas about the quantity and quality of education often cause to reduce the achievement motivation in students. So care must be taken to free the society from these prejudices and biases.

Development of Socio-Cultural Status - Socio cultural status also influences the achievement motivation of the students. Different society and cultural groups have their own goal, standard or criterion. The pupil from these groups represent their society and culture and try to achieve and stick to their own goal, standard of criterion. So if the socio cultural status can improved the achievement motivation of the pupil can also be improved. Over and above, for higher achievement motivation the meaningful, joyful experience in the educational level will lead to greater satisfaction and the greater utility value of the system of education will develop the strongest base for achievement motivation.

Hence need specific and utility specific educational system will vary highly be appreciated. The system and method of curriculum having more scope for job opportunities will also be the great source for developing need to achieve motive in students.

Suggestions for Further Research

The study was concerned with school academic achievement of secondary school students but all the aspects considered as correlates to academic achievement could not be concerned due to some limitation in investigation. Therefore some valuable recommendation is recommended for further research.

- 1. Prediction of school achievement:** A study pertaining to this could be conducted to elaborate same of the other correlates like cognitive style of functioning, psycho social constraints, creativity, school and home environment, socio-economic factors and other psycho sociological factors like anxiety, intelligence, parental attitude, educational aspiration, study habits, locus of control etc. could be considered in respect of their predicting variables to the criterion of academic achievement.
- 2. Development of standardized tool:** Further researches may be conducted to develop standardized school achievement tests in view of course and curriculum at a particular level for better appraisal instead of considering school examination marks as the criterion measure of academic achievement.
- 3. Wider implication of the study:** For wider implication of the study further studies could be taken, taking other strata of the population besides gender, locale and management and larger sample of representative nature covering more districts and large number of students.
- 4. Development of norms:** Ample scope for further researches are recommended to modify and re-standardized the tools including more dimensions, items and more developed psychometric techniques and norms could be developed for the following tools. Comparative studies might be conducted on Secondary school stream reading under different board, CBSE, ICSE, Madrassa Boards, State Boards of Examination.
- 5. Researches of interaction nature:** Researches concerning the interaction effects of the variables along with other attribute variables could be conducted to magnify the prediction studies with regression analysis where by individual components wise prediction to the criterion measure could be assessed.

References

- Aborl, D.N. (1977). A Study of Achievement Motivation in Relation to Intelligence, Vocational Interests, Achievement, Sex and Socio-economic Status. *Third Survey of Research in Education* (p. 317). New Delhi: NCERT.
- Chauhan, S.S. (1984). A Comparative Study of the Achievement Motivation of ST and SC Students of Himachal Pradesh in relation to their Intelligence and Socio-economic Status. in M.B. Buch (Ed.) *Fourth Survey of Research in Education* (Pp. 354, 355), New Delhi: NCERT.
- Chhetri, S. (2012). *Self concept and Achievement Motivation of Adolescents and their relationship with Academic Achievement*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Utkal University, Odisha.
- Dahal, M. (2012). Effect of Home Environment in School Achievement of Elementary School Children. *Himalayan Journal of Social Sciences*. Vol.2., Issue 1.

Gender Deconstruction as a Tool for Ending Sexual Violence Against Women

*Dr. Chongtick Lachungpa**

Abstract

Violence against women is one of the most pressing issues of our society today. It hounds the women through its different forms - rape being one of the most heinous one. The purpose of the study is to delve into this Social crime and explore the problems faced by the victims both at the time of crime and post crime. The unequal power relation between the male and female is the result of gendered roles constructed by the patriarchal society. Rape is one form of assertion of the male power over women. Hence the study concludes that sexual violence against women can be addressed by gender deconstruction through the changed mindset of the society, gender-just governmental policies, role of State and non-State institutions/actors, school text books, sensitization of the civil society, initiating legal literacy drives, and proper implementation of the rape laws. Suggestions for policy alternatives also figure in the study.

Keywords: *Sexual Violence, Rape, Patriarchy, Gender Deconstruction*

Introduction

Gender is a social construct which grants meaning to the biological sex. In other words norms and expectations define male and female nature and behaviour (Geetha, 2009). In fact "gender construction starts with assignment to a sex category on the basis of what the genitalia look like at birth" (Lorber, 1994). Gendering begins with the names, dresses and roles assigned to girls and boys by the society. Further the codes of behaviour are constructed differently like, "Boys must not cry, girls must never be seen without underwear. Boys can run, jump, climb trees, girls are asked to be careful" (Geetha, 2009). Such social conditioning of the minds of the children reinforces the gender construction. Religious texts also play a prominent role in reinforcing male superiority. Objectification and stereotypical depiction of women in the media contribute to continued reification of the normative. School curriculum undermine the girls wherein the boys dominate the narratives (John, 2008). The economic structure thrives on the public/private split and women's access to the public remains marginal in multiple ways. Men continue to be regarded as bread-winners for the family and working women are saddled with the burden of the second shift (Hochschild, 2003). In the political arena too it is evident from the mere 11% women representation

*Assistant Professor, Deptt. of Political Science, Sikkim Government College, Tadong-737101 Gangtok, Sikkim, Email id: chonglpa@gmail.com, Mobile no.: 9434021323

in the 16th Lok Sabha, that there is gender discrimination (PRS,2016). Therefore Gender construction translates to gender biases in upbringing, schooling, social customs, roles in society, economic and political arena which ultimately results into devaluation of women and gender discrimination. Devaluation of women is not the result of biological sex with which one is born but the result of social process which is ingrained into the general social structure with a purpose - subordination of women. Hence, Social Construction Feminism underline that gendering is pervasive to the extent in the social structure that many believe it to be biological and natural.

Theoretical Framework

This paper argues for a feminist understanding of rape in order to suggest concrete policy measures to address the issues around sexual violence against women. This section reviews existing feminist theorizations around rape to further our understanding. According to Radical feminists rape does more harm to women as a group (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2013). It is one form of assertion of authority over women in the male-female power equation. This unequal power relation results in discrimination of women (Goel, Kaur, Sultana, 2006). In most cases the victims do not speak out and opt to remain silent because of the fear of social stigma. This further perpetuates the menace and discrimination on women. One of the forms of Patriarchal control over women is through threat of violence and rape.

Sex-positive feminist ideas are also relevant for rethinking the patriarchal constructions of rape by not identifying sex as the problem but the attitude towards sex as the problematic that needs to be re-theorized. The core of sex positive feminism can be captured in the following words, "sex can be beautiful, it can be ugly, it can be difficult to deal with or easy to understand, some kinds of sex widely misunderstood, some kinds of sex widely stereotyped, some people are really into sex, and some people aren't but most importantly all kinds of sex are okay as long as they happen among consenting adults" (Thorn, 2011). It means that as long as sex is healthy and explicitly consensual, it is a positive thing. Further its aim is to remove stigma and shame from all sexual choice (Women and Gender Advocacy Centre, Colorado State University, 2016). The emphasis is on 'consent'. Do females really have a choice? How important is her consent? The gender socialization in the patriarchal society undermines the female's consent and choice. Sex Positive Feminism is against sexual violence since it does not involve consent.

Both Post Structural Feminist Theories and Post Modernist Feminist theories agree that gender discrimination prevails in the society and needs mechanism to improve the status of women.

Sexual Violence against Women

The Indian Penal Code defines rape as forced sexual intercourse with a woman under the following circumstances: against her will; without her consent; with her consent obtained by putting fear of death or of hurt; with her consent, when the man knows that he is not her husband and that her consent is given because she believes that he is another man to whom she is or believes herself to be lawfully married; with her consent under intoxication given by the rapist whereby she is unable to understand the nature and consequence to which she gives her consent; with or without consent of a girl who is under eighteen years of age; and when she is unable to communicate consent (The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013). It can happen to 'anyone' and in 'any kind of situations' - family, workplace, anywhere and even in the supposed to be 'safe' State custody. "Violence against women in police custody is common and includes sexual violence, inappropriate surveillance, strip searches conducted by men and demands for sexual acts in exchange for privileges or basic necessities" (UN Department of Public Information, November, 2011). It is a kind of violation that takes away the individual's rights over her body and choice. It violates women's basic human right to live with sexual dignity and without fear (Mohanty, 2009). Such sexual violence stands as an obstacle in the development of women and society at large.

Statistics on Rape : The reported cases of rape against women in the country according to the National Crime Records Bureau stands as follows in the five years:

The figures in the above table reflect the increase in the crime against women. The actual figures would be much higher if the unreported cases are taken into account. Further, the figures also show the reported cases of assault on women with the intent to outrage her modesty, insult to the modesty of women and attempt to commit rape. The data speaks about the plight of women. There is an increase in Percentage variation in 2014 over 2013 in regard to rape and assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty. For the first time in 2014, National Crime Records Bureau started collecting data for reported cases of attempt to commit rape and the figure stood at 4234!!

Table 1 Crime against Women in India

SL.NO.	Crime Heads	Years					Percentage variation 2014 over 2013
		2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	
1.	Rape	22,172	24,206	24,923	33,707	36,735	9.0
2.	Attempted to Rape					4234	
3.	Assault to women to her/their monestry	40,613	42,968	45,351	70,739	82,235	16.3
4.	Insult to the modesty of woman	9,961	8,570	9,173	12,589	9,735	-22.7

Source: National Crime Records Bureau Ministry of Home Affairs (year 2014)

Types of Rape

Source: Crime in India., 2014 Compendium, National Crime Records Bureau, Ministry of Home Affairs

It is evident from the above figure that rape can occur anywhere and it can be committed by anybody irrespective of the victim's age. The worst kind is the incest rape wherein the culprit has a blood relation with the victim. From the table it shows that 674 reported cases of incest rape in 2014. This figure is an increase when compared to 536 cases in 2013. It is also sad to note that rapes are committed even in the places regarded as 'safe' like in the custody of police, hospital and judicial custody and many other places supposedly regarded safe. In the year 2014 the custodial rapes stood at 197 and it was also the first time that the NCRB started collecting data for reported cases of custodial rapes. Another gruesome kind of rape is the gang rape and 2346 cases were reported in the same year. Remaining 33,518 covered other rape cases. NCRB data on child rapes show an appalling and nerve wrenching figures of 8,541 (2012), 12,363 (2013) and 13,766 (2014) !! Further Delhi reported as many as 1813 rape cases (per one lakh of the population) in 2014. What is shocking is that NCRB data shows 524 girls under the age of 6 as rape victims!!

Consequences of Rape

Rape is a harrowing experience for the victim, very degrading, humiliating and takes a toll on her dignity. The ill effects of such crime percolates to the family and society. The degree of psychological distress it brings to the victim and to her family is unfathomable (Koss, 1993). Violation of bodily and sexual autonomy is one of the central harm done by rape. In other words rape does not treat victim as a person but as an object with pure sexual function. It is a form of mechanism which dehumanizes and objectifies the woman. The trauma does not stop with the victim but percolates down to the people who help the rape victim too in the form of vicarious trauma and even researchers working on such crime experiences the pain (Nelson, 2014). The increasing crime on women tends to create Rape Culture in the society wherein society blames the victims of sexual assault and normalizes male sexual violence. This puts the women in a very vulnerable position.

Victims go through a huge feeling of humiliation and shame. If one does not get timely support then there is high chances of the victim going into depression and sometimes leading to suicide. Some victims take to substance abuse and punish themselves.

The fear of social stigma on her and her family pulls back the victim from reporting. As long as the victim remains silent, the abuse continues. Cultural judgment of the victim as dirty woman or damaged good is humiliating and degrading. Rape can aptly be equated to a terrorist institution which

terrorizes and intimidates the victim.(Griffin,1971) .The main aim of rape is to maintain the silence of the women and compliance with their subjugated place in the society.

The aftermath of the crime is most painful for the victim both ways- whether she chooses to report and seek help or whether she chooses to remain silent. A thought stirring suffering which the victim faces post-rape is the Secondary Wounding (Louise,2006). It comes in many forms which further crushes and deflates the already battered soul of the rape victim. It could come from friends, well wishers, strangers, people working in police, courts, hospital or even NGOs. Secondary wounding creep in, in the form of denial and disbelief of her story when a victim seeks help. The victim has to sometimes face statements that doubt whether she is exaggerating; that they don't believe it and that it could never happen to her. Yet another form of secondary wounding is blaming the victim and questioning about the kind of dress she was wearing and even to an extent of blaming her for provoking it. Discounting the victim's suffering is one of the secondary woundings whereby society lessens the magnitude of the abuse she went through. It comes from statements telling her that she was lucky enough not have been killed or that her situation is better than another victim. Betrayal of confidence of the victim by the people on whom she had trusted and bared it all with her story, can have a very deep impact on the psychological aspect of the victim (Shannon, 2007). Therefore, Secondary wounding makes the victim feel ashamed and helpless, she begins to blame herself for the rape.

Gender Deconstruction as a Tool to End Sexual Violence against Women

Rape can occur regardless of the victim's age, marital status, caste, relation, culture, class, economic status, religion and place. It controls the women physically and psychologically. The apathetic attitude of men and society in general towards women is rooted in the gender construed society. According to World Bank Data "women who are aged 15-44 are more at risk from rape and domestic violence than from cancer, car accidents, war and malaria" (UN Department of Public Information,2011). Therefore the most important task is to work towards Gender Deconstruction and change people's perception of woman. This will in turn translate in improving women's status and value in the society.

Gender Deconstruction is a process through which the gender equity can be achieved by deconstructing the fixed norms and expectations attached to male and female by the society. For

instance Liberal Feminism calls for redressing the gender and ethnic imbalance in workplaces by encouraging men to get trained as nurses, teachers and for secretarial work, and women in fields like engineering, construction and police force.(Lorber,1997)

Table 2 India's Standing in the Global Gender Gap

Simple		Overall	Economy	Education	Health	Politics
Year	No. of Countries	Rank	Rank	Rank	Rank	Rank
2015	145	108	139	125	143	9
2014	142	114	134	126	141	15
2013	136	101	124	120	135	9
2012	135	105	123	121	134	17
2011	135	113	131	121	134	19
2010	134	112	128	120	132	23
2009	134	114	127	121	134	24
2008	130	113	125	116	126	25
2007	128	114	122	116	126	21
2006	115	98	110	102	103	20

Source: The Global Gender Gap Report 2015, World Economic Forum

Gender Gap is the disproportionate difference or the disparity between the female and males in terms various indicators of development. The Global Gender Gap Report 2015 by World Economic Forum puts India at 108 rank out of 145 countries. India's rank in economy, education, health and politics stood 139,125,143 and 9 respectively. Looking at the ranking in the last decade, not much change can be seen. The data above has a direct bearing on the women's status and value in the society. Therefore women's status needs to be raised through successful policies in regard to women in the field of economy, education, health and politics. According to WEF in the area of sex ratio at birth (female / male), India's ranking is 143 out of 145 which is a very dismal picture which clearly shows the low value of female children in India. Looking at the wide gender gap, it becomes all the more important to close in the gender gap.

Gender Deconstruction can take place first within the family. Bringing up both girl and boy child

equally is one of the most important task at hand. We should stop giving too much importance on gender roles and stop gendering in every aspect of day to day life. Placing responsibility on the civil society and emphasizing on constructive role played by the State and non-state institutions in terms of women's well being, will also bring about change in the condition of women. Gender equity translates into better status of the women. Better status of women will bring a decline in social crimes against women.

Suggestions for Policy Alternatives and Mechanism for Changing the Attitude of the Society towards Rape and Women.

- Role of local authorities such as police, panchayats and councillors form the most crucial part in the event of rape. They should take earnest responsibility in handling sexual violence cases. Policy provisions should be framed in a pro-victim mode. Immediate help should be made available and questions of jurisdiction among others should not hamper the registration of the case, immediate counselling, medical aid and provision of safe-house if need be, should be made mandatory. Thus saving the precious time which would help the police nab the culprit faster and also timely help is made possible to the victim.
- Proper implementation of rape laws should be carried out without the streaks of patriarchal leanings.
- Social responsibility could be inculcated in the society. A mechanism or a law to involve the whole community in combating such crime should be in place.
- Proper rehabilitation of the victims is very important for the healing process and coming to terms with life and move on.
- Being more sensitive and caring towards the victim while handling the victim's report by the police, court and NGOs is very crucial. Giving a patient hearing and support makes it much easier for the victim to come to terms with life.
- Gender sensitization of the civil society is the sine qua non for gender deconstruction.
- Sensitizing the women about their legal and constitutional rights can equip them with ways for fighting injustice.
- Encourage victims to come forward and report the event to authorities because the crime will increase if they maintain silence.

- Role of media should be more sensitive to victims and also while portraying women.
- Spreading awareness about gender equality to school children.
- Introduction of women empowerment in school books. Chapters pertaining to women's contribution and role should be included in the syllabi of the school books and thereby inculcating values in the young minds about women.
- The judiciary should be able to give justice without patriarchal biases.
- Involving more NGOs in imparting awareness in the society about women issues and gender equity would be a welcome step towards gender deconstruction.
- There should be training for all involved namely police, judges, doctors, psychologists, social service providers, civil servants, local level civil servants and members local self government so that there is better understanding of women's rights and plight of rape victims.
- Inclusive policies in every aspect of policy making should be given utmost importance to improve the status of women in the society.
- Reformation of Rape law is needed which should be able to act as an effectual deterrent. At present in India the rapist can be imprisoned for seven years to ten years depending on the severity of the act. Most of the time the culprit get away with lesser punishment.
- Deconstruction of gender identities and roles which centers around femininity and masculinity should be minimized and gradually eradicated . Klaus Schwab , founder and executive chairman of the World Economic Forum (2015) aptly says that "...we need a world where women's contributions and ideals are as valued as those of men. Gender parity in our thinking and actions will be critical in helping to ensure that the future is served by humanity and not threatened by it."

Conclusion

We need to think of more constructive ways of organizing social life than reproducing and reinforcing heteronormative gender roles. It will also continually perpetuate existing hierarchical social arrangements that keep women in subordination. It is thus imperative that we question these arrangements to bring about social change since "Reconceptualizing gender not as a simple property of individuals but as an integral dynamic of social orders implies a new perspective on the entire

network of gender relations...." (West and Zimmerman, 1987). Simone de Beauvoir rightly (1953) says, "we are not born but become women (and men)". Gender deconstruction thus remains a distant yet desirable goal.

References

Books:

- Beauvoir, Simone de, (1953). *The Second Sex*. translated by H.M. Parshley, New York: Knopf
- Birner, Alexis, (2016). "Boys don't wear dresses!": *Deconstructing gender representations in an elementary school classroom*, Canadian Journal for New Scholars in Education, cjinse-rcje.ca accessed on 5.12.16
- Brownmiller, Susan, (1975). *Against our will: men, women and rape*. New York : Fawcett Columbine
- Chatterjee, M, (2006). *Violence Against Women*. Jaipur: Aavishkar Publishers
- Devi, Uma, K. (Ed) (2005). *Violence against women: Human Rights Perspective*. New Delhi: Serials Publications
- diglib.bis.uni-oldenburg.de/pub/unireden/ur07/kap1.pdf accessed on 8/11/16
- Geetha, V, (2007). *Patriarchy*. Calcutta: Stree
- Geetha, V, (2009). *Gender*. Kolkata: Stree
- Ghosh, Dwaipayan, Sunday, 2nd October, 2016, *4 years after Park St. rape, prime accused held in Greater Noida*, Sunday Times, Kolkata
- Goel, Aruna., Kaur, Manvinder., Sultana, Ameer (Eds.) (2006). *Violence Against Women: issues and perspective*. New Delhi: Deep and Deep Publishers
- Goonesekere, Savitri, (Ed) (2004). *Violence, Law and women's rights in South Asia*. United Nations Development Fund For Women, New Delhi: Sage Publications
- Griffin, Susan, (1971). *Rape: The All American Crime*. www.unz.org/pub/Ramparts-71-sep-00026. accessed on 06.12.16
- Hochschild, Arlie Russell, (2003). *The Second Shift*. London: Penguin books.
- <https://jenseyatvajameh.files.wordpress.com/2008/07/sakhtareejtemaiejenseyat.pdf>, accessed on 6/12/16.
- Jackson, Stevi and Jones, Jackie (Eds), (1998). *Contemporary Feminist Theories*. New York: Edinburg University Press

Jewkes, Dunkle, Nduna, Shai,(2010). *Intimate Partner Violence, Relationship power equity, and incidence of HIV infection in young women in south Africa: a cohort Study*, www.thelancet.com accessed on 10.9.16

John, Mary E. (Ed), (2008). *India: Women's Studies in India*. New Delhi: Penguin Books

Koss, Mary P ,(1993). *Rape: Scope, Impact, Interventions, and Public Policy Responses*. [psycnet.apa.org>journals>amp](http://psycnet.apa.org/journals/amp), accessed on 8.8.16

Kumar,Radha,(1993).*The History Doing*. New Delhi:Zubaan

Lorber,Judith,(1994). "*Night to his Day*": *The Social Construction Gender*,

Lorber,Judith,(1997).The variety of feminisms and their contribution to gender equality,

Louise, (2006). *Forms of secondary wounding and overcoming secondary wounding exercise: help for rape & sexual abuse victims & survivor*, Pandora's Project, file:///C:/Users/user/Documents/Secondary%20Wounding%20Pandora's%20Project.html accessed on 16.08.16

Mohanty, Bedabati, (2009). *Violence Against Women :Analysis of Contemporary Realities*. New Delhi: Kanishka Publishing House.

Narasaiah, Lakshmi, M, (2004). *Empowerment for Women*. New Delhi: Discovery Publishing House

Nelson, Terri Spahn, (2014).Vicarious Trauma: Bearing Witness To Another's Trauma, [www.azcadv.org>2014/06](http://www.azcadv.org/2014/06) accessed on 15/11/16

Newspapers:

Paxton, Pamela and Hughes, M. Melanie (2007). *Women, Politics, And Power: A Global Perspective*. California: Pine Forge press

Rai, Sandeep, Monday,17 October 2016, *Rape survivor on way to court shot at by 4 accused*, The Times Of India, Kolkata.

Rampton, Martha,(2015). Four Waves of Feminism, <http://www.pacificu.edu/about-us/news-events/four-waves-feminism> assessed on 5/12/16

Ray,Raka (ed),.(2012). *Handbook of Gender*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press

Sangari,Vaid (eds.),(1989). *Recasting Women: Essays in colonial History*. New Delhi: Zubaan

Sarkar, Suparno,(2015). *Delhi retains 'Rape capital' tag as cases rise 25% , Nagaland safest for women*, <http://www.ibtimes.co.in/delhi-retains-rape-capital-tag-cases-rise-25-nagaland-safest-women-says-ncrb-report-643934#vz9bBdceVFGgE3ekf.97> accessed on 5.08.16

- Saunders Kriemild (ed.), (2004). *Feminist Post-Development Thought*. New Delhi: Zubaan
- Tharu, Susie and Lalita, K. (Eds), (1993). *Women Writing In India: 600B.C. To The Present, Volume 1 and 2*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press
- Thorn, Clarisse,(2011). *Feminism,Sex,Sexual Assault: Interview with a sex-positive feminist*, www.feministe.us/blog/archives/2011/12/16-interview-with-a-sex-positive-feminist/ accessed on 7.11.16
- Visvanathan , Duggan, Nisonoff,Wiegersma (eds.) (1997). *The Women & Gender Development Reader*. New Delhi: Zubaan

Websites:

- West and Zimmerman, (1987).*Doing Gender*. Gender and Society,Vol.1, No.2(June, 1987)pp. 125-151,<https://www.jstor.org/stable/189945> accessed on 12.12.16
-, (Friday 28 October 2016). *Still Unfair*. The Telegraph, VOL.XXXV NO.109, Kolkata
-, (2011).*Violence Against Women*, United Nations Secretary General's Campaign Unite to End Violence women, DPI/2546A,November 2011. [endviolence.un.org>pdf>pressmaterials](http://endviolence.un.org/pdf/pressmaterials) accessed on 8/11/16
-, (2016). *Sex Positivity*. Women and Gender Advocacy Centre, Colorado State University, www.wgac.colostate.edu/sex-positivity accessed on 8/12/16
-, 2016. *Profile of the 16th Lok Sabha*, PRS Legislative Research, www.prsindia.prg>media>media-updates assessed on 6/12/16
-, Monday,31 October 2016,*Girl raped*, The Telegraph, Calcutta.
-, *It will take another 118 years to close the economic gender gap*, World Economic Forum, www.telegraph.co.uk/finance/economics/12003599/It-will-take-another-118-years-to-close-the-economic-gender-gap-WEF-says.html accessed on 5.11.16
-,2015.*Feminism and Education*, www.historylearningsite.co.uk/sociology/education-and/feminism-and-education/ accessed on 6/12/16
-, *To be scarred or not to be scarred? making sense of secondary wounding*, healingafterrape.net/healing-after-rape.wound.html accessed on 6.11.16.
-,(2013). *Feminist Perspective on Rape*, Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, <http://plato.stanford.edu/entries/feminism-rape/> accessed on 27.10.16
-,What is Rape Culture?, women against violence, Rape Crisis Centre. <http://www.ca/what-is-rape-culture/> accessed on 13.08.16

Perception of Secondary School Teachers for Generating Learning Friendly Classroom Environment

Dr. Mitanjali Sahoo*

Abstract

Classroom learning environment is a complex exercise in the process of education. It demands talent, skills, energy and ability from teachers to manage classrooms because it directly deals with the behaviours of learners. An attempt has been made in the present study to obtain the experience based perception of the secondary school teachers about the generation of learning friendly classroom environment in relation to their gender, teaching experience and academic stream variation and to find out the difference between the actual and preferred classroom environment as perceived by them. 150 secondary school teachers were selected randomly from different government and private schools of Gangtok city, Sikkim. An opinionnaire developed by Mahapatra and Mahapatra (2008) was used in the study. The female and less experienced teachers showed positive attitude for generating learning friendly classroom environment. A huge gap was found between the actual and preferred classroom environment as perceived by the teachers. Recommendations were provided on the basis of the practical situations and feasibilities for implementing in the classrooms.

Key Words:- Perception, Secondary School Teachers, Learning Friendly Classroom Environment.

Introduction

Knowledge is actively constructed by the learners. To optimise meaningful learning, it becomes imperative that a learning friendly classroom environment should be provided for the learners so that he/she may construct the knowledge in a way he/she is expected to construct. Individuals cannot be considered in isolation, divorced from the society.

Learning is perceived as a cultural apprenticeship and that cognition is argued to be situated in the specific context. In this connection the classroom is the crucial social unit where the constructs that are advanced by the scientific community are mostly negotiated. Thus for the negotiation to go through successfully, it is essential that a learning friendly environment be generated inside the classroom. Classroom learning environment is a complex exercise in the process of education. It demands talent, skills, energy and ability from teachers to manage classrooms because it directly deals with the behaviours of learners. Human behaviour is the most complex phenomenon. Teachers with highly

*Assistant Professor, Centre for Education, Central University of South Bihar. E-mail- mitanjali_sahoo@rediffmail.com

practical vision, strategies, skills and knowledge can manage classroom effectively (Tan, Parsons, Hinson, and Sardo-Brown, 2003). The term classroom learning friendly environment refers to all those decisions that teachers take to facilitate the learning process and to provide the students maximum opportunity for learning (Krause,Bochner, and Duchesne, 2003).Canter and Canter (2001) stated thatthere are three goals of learning friendly classroom management i.e. (i) to create and maintain a highly supportive learning environment (ii) to promote a safe classroom community so that students' interest, motivation and involvement in the learning process are maintained (iii) to allow the student to establish relationships openly and to set targets for themselves. This situation will enable to discuss their needs with teachers and also feel comfortable to intellectual risks. For this purpose teachers can establish rules and routines.

Teachers' Perception for Generating Learning Friendly Environment

Some examples of the previous studies conducted have been described here which elaborates upon the various aspects of teachers' perception for generating a friendly environment:

Mahapatra and Mahapatra (2008) conducted a study on science teacher's perception under Indian conditions a conceptual model for the learning environment and found that science teachers had more perception regarding pedagogy related issues. As per the teachers perception they regard all the six categories student related, pedagogy related, teaching strategy related, teacher related, student empowerment related and creativity related as equally important for generating learning friendly classroom environment.

Eggen and Kauchak (2004) viewed that teachers usually encounter disciplinary problems during classroom teaching process. One of the best ways to deal with behaviour problems is establishment of classroom rules and procedures. Procedures help teachers in establishing routines for students for example turning papers, asking for questions, sharpening pencils, doing group or pair activities. Rules provide sense of regularity and organization for students and teachers.

A teacher's behaviour has a great impact on his classroom climate. Teachers often spend too much time on how they want their classrooms to look or their students to behave that they neglect to focus on attuning themselves to their classroom climate. Teachers are a central variable in defining a classroom climate because they set the tone for their students to follow. Once teachers organize their classes to promote learning, establish a climate of respect and safety and behave in a way they wish their students to follow, it is up to the students to create the classroom climate that is specific to their

personalities. Every classroom climate is different because it relies so heavily on the variables within it. Students make up the most populous of these variables and, when they feel they are in a safe and respectful environment, they will express themselves freely. Students' personalities are integral in a unique and successful classroom climate. Classroom environment is perceived from an interpersonal perspective on teaching which concerns creating and maintaining a positive, warm classroom atmosphere conducive to learning. The focus is on the relationship between students and teachers. Teachers have both direct and an indirect influence on students. As a result they contribute to the learning environment of these students. For example, teaching behaviour, teaching styles and student perception of the learning environment have been studied and found to be related to student learning (Brophy & Good, 1986).

Huang (2003) conducted a study on an assessment of teacher's perception of secondary environment and found that Science teacher's perception of school environment reflects the affective domain of science education and deserves greater emphasis.

Maslowski (2003) conducted a study on classroom climate and perceived class environment as 'the collective perceptions of teachers with respect to the mutual relationships within the classroom, the organisation of the lessons and the learning tasks of the students'. It is quite important to mention that the relationship between students and teachers is closely related to the classroom environment.

Good and Prophy (2002) found that learning friendly Classroom environment is organizing space, time and materials to facilitate effective instruction. It is a highly difficult task, because a teacher has to cope with many students with individual differences. They have different interest and choices.

Tan (2001) found that for maintaining a good friendly classroom learning environment and for solutions of classroom problems, teachers must create conducive learning environment where students find respect, care, meaning and opportunity for personal and social growth. For this purpose, both teachers and students should be able to interact with each other easily under the established rules, procedures and regulations.

Dharmadasa (2000) conducted a study on teacher's perspectives on constructivist teaching and learning and found that teachers in realistic situations may view learning friendly environment in teaching as a challenge, an additional burden, and a disrupting source for classroom discipline.

Saad (1999) found that classroom environment is not a place where only transfer of information takes place rather it encompasses other essential aspects of learning such as physical space, materials,

attitudes of teacher and the taught, feelings and emotions, and other social dynamics of life. All these form important characteristics of the teaching and learning experiences.

Neary and Halvorsen (1995) revealed that the best environments for learning are those in which students are motivated by the teacher and learning is active and information is presented in a manner that recognizes the diversity of each student. Teacher need to recognize, identify and understand that each student (special education or general education) attaches to the learning process at different levels and rates. Special education students bring with them into the classroom a sort of instructional manual on how to create an environment fitted to meet their individual needs.

According to **Moos (1979)** the relationship between students and teachers is an important dimension of class climate. Most distinguishes six dimensions of classroom atmosphere. These six dimensions are relationships within the classroom, personal development and goal orientation, and maintenance and changes within the system.

When teachers create an environment of care, love and democracy inside the classroom, students become highly motivated, which results in their better learning. This habit of friendliness usually prevails in reflective teachers. Teachers are aware of the intentions of their students. They plan the learning experiences according to the needs and expectations of the students which help in attaining the attention of students during teaching and learning. In an active learning environment students actively participate in the process of teaching and learning which is the one of the main goals of education.

Since teachers are the key human input to make the teaching learning process effective an attempt has been made by the investigator to obtain their experience based perception about the criteria for generating a learning friendly environment in the classroom.

The following research question has been asked for this purpose:

- Is there any difference in the perception of secondary school teachers for generating learning friendly classroom environment due to gender, teaching experience and academic stream variation?
- Is there a difference between actual and preferred classroom environment as perceived by the teachers?

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives were stated for the conduct of the study.

- To assess the perception of secondary school teachers for generating learning friendly classroom environment.
- To find out the significant differences in the perception of secondary school teachers for generating learning friendly classroom environment in relation to gender, experience and academic stream variation both totally and component wise.
- To find out the difference between the actual and preferred classroom environment as perceived by the teachers.

Formulation of Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the perception of secondary school teachers for generating learning friendly environment in relation to their gender variation both totally and component wise.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the perception of secondary school teachers for generating learning friendly environment in relation to their teaching experience variation both totally and component wise.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the perception of secondary school teachers for generating learning friendly environment in relation to their academic stream variation both totally and component wise.

Ho₄: There is no difference between the actual and preferred classroom environment as perceived by the teachers.

The Sample

150 secondary school teachers (75 Male and 75 Female) were selected randomly from both government and private schools of Gangtok City, Sikkim. The institutional climate which also influences the perception of teachers was considered while selecting the sample.

The Tool

To obtain the opinion of the teachers for generating learning friendly classroom environment, the opinionnaire of Mahapatra and Mahapatra (2008) was used in the study. The opinionnaire was divided into 2 parts (part A and part B). Part A consists of 45 items with 6 dimensions like student related, pedagogy related, teaching strategy related, teacher related, student empowerment related

and creativity related issues. In brief, the Students' Related (SR) issues have 10 items, Pedagogy Related (PR) issues have 10 items, Teaching Strategy Related (TSR) issues have 8 items, Teacher Related (TR) issues have 6 items, Student Empowerment Related (SER) issues have 9 items and Creativity Related (CR) issues have 2 items. The content validity of the opinionnaire was ascertained by a group of experts and its reliability coefficient was found to be 0.89. The second half of the tool dealt with responses provided by each participant suggesting five activities/methods/strategies which will promote generation of learning friendly classroom environment.

The tool was administered in a relaxed environment. The teachers were asked not to write their name and address on their respective opinionnaire sheets with the aim that they might freely express their views. Forty five minutes time was allowed to complete the first part of the opinionnaire and another fifteen minutes time was allowed to complete the open-ended second part of the tool.

Results and Discussion

Part 'A' of the Opinionnaire

So far as the scoring of the 45 items in the first part of the opinionnaire was concerned, marks 2, 1 and 0 were given to the responses "agree", "undecided" and "disagree" for all the positive statements and reverse is the case for negative statements. Thus the maximum marks for the first part was 90. The maximum marks, average marks of the respondents, standard deviation, coefficient of variation as well as the average marks as a percentage of the maximum marks for each category of items, as obtained after the analysis of the responses were presented in table 1.

Table 1: Analysis of the responses by the teachers to the first part (45 items) of the opinionnaire

Dimensions of items	SR	PR	TSR	TR	SER	CR
Number of items	10	10	8	6	9	2
Maximum marks= No of items x 2	20	20	16	12	18	4
Average mark secured Dimension wise	18.38	18.98	13.54	10.5	16.03	3.65
Standard Deviation	2.89	2.56	2.19	1.82	2.16	1.009
Coefficient of variation	15.72	13.48	16.17	17.33	13.47	27.64
Average mark as a percentage of maximum mark	91.9	94.9	84.62	87.5	89.05	91.25

It was revealed from the above table that the values of coefficient of variation in all the six dimensions like SR, PR, TSR, TR, SER and CR were found to be 15.72, 13.48, 16.17, 17.33, 13.47 and 27.64 respectively. The values of the coefficient of variation ranged from 13 to 27 which indicated that responses were fairly consistent.

To bring the scores against all the categories of responses to the same scale so as to assess their relative preferences by the teachers, the average marks as a percentage of the corresponding maximum marks were calculated and were found to be 91.9%, 94.9%, 87.37%, 92.16%, 89.05%, 91.25% in case of SR, PR, TSR, TR, SER and CR dimensions respectively. It was revealed that the percentage of scores against the 6 categories range between 87.37 to 94.9%. This indicated that the respondents perceive that each category is very important to generate learning friendly classroom environment.

To assess the significant differences in the perception of teachers in different dimensions and in case of total the 't' ratios were calculated and were discussed as follows:

I. Academic stream variation on perception of secondary school teachers for generating learning friendly classroom environment

One of the objectives of the study was to find out if there exists significance in the perception of the secondary school teachers for generating learning friendly classroom environment in relation to academic stream variation. In order to test the significant difference in the mean scores of the perception of secondary school teachers in generating learning friendly classroom environment, X^2 was calculated both totally and component wise. The X^2 calculated in case of total, student related, pedagogy related, teaching strategy related, teacher related, student empowerment related and creativity related dimensions were found to be 0.3, 0.12, 0.43, 0.14, 0.13, 0.13 and 0.004 respectively. In all the cases the X^2 was not significant and was concluded that there existed no significant difference in the perception of arts, science and commerce teachers both totally and component wise. Mean difference could not be significant due to less magnitude of differences among the means. The science teachers were found to give more stress on pedagogy, teaching strategy and creativity related issues. Arts and commerce teachers were found to emphasise on student related and student empowerment related issues. This may be due to the nature of the subjects

and the teachers.

ii. Gender and teaching experience difference in the perception of secondary school teachers for generating learning friendly classroom environment

Table 2: Summary of 't' ratios component wise on the sample in relation to gender and experience variation on perception of teachers for generating learning friendly classroom environment.

Component	Sample	Sub-sample	N	Mean	SD	SE _D	T	Remark
Student related	Gender	Male	75	17.81	2.51	0.462	2.49	p<0.05
		Female	75	18.96	3.13			
	Experience	<10	90	18.90	2.60	0.334	6.23	p<0.01
		>10	60	16.82	1.50			
Pedagogy related	Gender	Male	75	18.92	2.24	0.417	0.31	NS
		Female	75	19.05	2.85			
	Experience	<10	90	19.82	2.30	0.344	4.3	P<0.01
		>10	60	18.34	1.90			
Teaching Strategy related	Gender	Male	75	14.34	2.18	0.333	4.77	P<0.05
		Female	75	14.34	1.91			
	Experience	<10	90	14.98	1.80	0.272	7.21	P<0.01
		>10	60	13.02	1.52			
Teacher related	Gender	Male	75	11.02	1.97	0.283	3.67	P<0.01
		Female	75	9.98	1.50			
	Experience	<10	90	14.98	1.80	0.271	7.21	p<0.01
		>10	60	31.02	1.52			
Student empowerment related	Gender	Male	75	17.74	1.94	0.289	4.91	p<0.01
		Female	75	16.32	1.61			
	Experience	<10	90	17.07	1.09	0.279	3.18	p<0.01
		>10	60	16.92	1.98			
Creativity related	Gender	Male	75	3.90	1.02	0.158	3.16	p<0.01
		Female	75	3.40	0.94			
	Experience	<10	90	3.1	0.98	0.14	14.2	NS
		>10	60	29	0.81			
Total	Gender	Male	75	82.14	5.42	1.03	2.08	P<0.05
		Female	75	84.39	7.13			
	Experience	<10	90	85.09	6.31	0.733	2.97	P<0.01
		>10	60	82.91	5.92			

It was revealed from the above table that gender difference in the perception of senior secondary teachers for generating learning friendly classroom environment was significant in case of student, teaching strategy, teacher, student empowerment, creativity related components and also for total sample. The female teachers perceived better than the male teachers towards generating learning friendly classroom environment in student related, pedagogy related and in case of total sample and in other cases male teachers perceived better. It may be due to the fact that the female teachers are more inclined towards teaching, show friendly attitude towards students and give more stress on teaching while the male teachers give more stress on students' empowerment, nurturing the creativity of the students. The study was in conformity with the studies conducted by Eggen and Kauchak (2004), Mahapatra and Mahapatra (2008) etc.

While teaching experience of the teachers was concerned, 't' ratio was found to be significant in case of total sample and all the components except creativity component. 't' ratio could not be significant with very less margin of 0.56. Hence it can be revealed that teaching experience of the teachers is an important factor in creating a learning friendly classroom environment. In the study the teachers having less than 10 years of teaching experience were found to show positive attitudes in creating a learning friendly classroom environment. It may be evident due to the fact that the teachers those who are fresh show more interest and give more stress on teaching learning process. They show their initiatives in student related, pedagogy, teaching strategy, creativity and empowering the students.

Analysis on Part 'B' of the Opinionnaire

With regard to the expected five suggestions from each of the teachers with respect to the second part of the opinionnaire, a total of 750 (i.e. 150x5) numbers of responses were expected. But only 682 numbers of responses were received. The responses were then classified under the six dimensions and were presented in table 3.

Table 3: Frequency and percentage distribution of the responses of the teachers

Dimensions	SR	PR	TSR	TR	SER	CR	Total
No of responses	84	146	158	126	112	57	682
% of responses	12.29	21.38	23.13	18.45	16.40	8.34	100

It was revealed from the above table that the number of responses as well as the percentage of the responses was more in teaching strategy and pedagogy related dimensions. That means the teachers felt these two as the most important dimensions for creating a learning friendly classroom environment. This is expected since the classroom teaching learning dynamics in most of the schools still reflect a teacher-centred transmissionist approach where the student is perceived as a passive receiver. Student related problems, their empowerment and creativity are given less importance towards generating a learning friendly classroom environment.

When the responses of the second part of the opinionnaire were compared with that of the first part, a huge difference in the responses of the teachers was found. It revealed that there are two discernable operational faces of each teacher, the ideal and the actual. The ideal deals with one's perception of what should be done and the actual depicts what is being done. The strategies suggested by the teacher for generating learning friendly classroom environment are not really feasible for implementing in their classrooms. As per the discussions with the teachers it was clear that the teachers are really in favour of providing learning friendly classroom environment for their students but they face problems like overcrowded classrooms, heavy workload, completing the syllabus and making the students ready for the examination, lack of support and opportunities, awareness about the strategies etc. Some teachers also opined that even if they are aware about the strategies, it was very difficult to implement in the real classroom situation.

From the above discussions it can be concluded that the teachers are the crucial agents of generating learning friendly classroom environment. Hence they have to be oriented at regular intervals so that they may be able to acquire the skill to implement the strategies for generating learning friendly classroom environment, enough resource materials have to be made available to the teachers so that they can take up self-enrichment activities according to their own suitability and convenience, efforts are to be made by the teachers for attaining expertise in nurturing the broad development of the students, administrative and academic support and empowerment have to be provided to the teachers to try out new ideas in classroom teaching. In this context if the workload of each teacher cannot be reduced, at least few periods in a week may be arranged for trying out the strategies for generating learning friendly classroom environment.

References

- Brophy, J.E, and Good, T.L (1986).Teacher behaviour and student achievement. In M.C. Wittrock (Ed.), *Handbook of research on teaching* (3rd ed., pp 328-275). New York: MacMillan.
- Canter, L, and M. Canter (2001). *Assertive discipline: Positive behaviour management for today's classrooms*. 3rd ed. Seal Beach, CA: Canter
- Dharmadasa, I. (2000). *Teachers Perspectives on Constructivist Teaching and Learning*. Abstract retrieved May, 25, 2006, from ERIC database.
- Eggen, P, and Kauchack, D. 2004. *Educational psychology: windows on classrooms*. 6th ed. New Jersey: Pearson
- Good, T, and Brophy (2002) *Looking in Classroom* 10th ed. Bistom and Bacon
- Huang, S.L.2006 An assessment of science teacher's perception of secondary environments in Taiwan. *International Journal of Science Education*, 28(1), 25-44
- Krause, K. L., Bochner, S., and Duchesne, S. (2003). *Educational psychology for learning and teaching*. Australia: Thomson
- Mahapatra, J. k and Mahaparta, M. 2008. A conceptual model for the learning environment. *Indian Education Review*, vol 44. No.2.
- Maslowski, R. (2003). *Klimaat in de klas*. [Classroom climate] .HSO.B4200-1/28.
- Moos, R. H (1979). *Evaluating educational environments*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass
- Neary, T and Halvorsen, A. (1995). What is Inclusion ? ERIC Digest, ED.393248.
- Saad, I. (1999). *Pakistan prospects and perspectives*. Karachi: Royal
- Tan, A. (2001). *Elementary school teachers' perception of desirable learning activities: A Singaporean perspective*. *Educational Research* 43 (1), 47-61.
- Tan O.S., Parsons, R.D., Hinson, S.L., and Sardo-Brown, D. (2003). *Educational psychology: A practitioner-researcher approach*. Australia: Thomson

Application of Quantitative Techniques for Road Network Connectivity Analysis in Dakshin Dinajpur District of West Bengal

Dr. Pradip Chouhan*

Abstract

Transport network and connectivity plays vital role in the economic development of any region. Dakshin Dinajpur is one of the backward and neglected districts of West Bengal. Road transport system is dominant here. Rail connectivity started in 2004 with the opening of Eklakhi- Balurghat broad gauge line. At present highly dominated and centralised road based mass transport services of this district help in the development of the local linkages system. In the multimodal public transport system of Dakshin Dinajpur district, the road based mass transport services are dominated by private sector companies with certain degree of public sector intervention. The varying degree of bus services along with auto-rickshaws and trekker services within Dakshin Dinajpur district, between Dakshin Dinajpur district and Kolkata and between Dakshin Dinajpur and other districts of West Bengal expresses the changing pattern of different levels of interaction among the areas. An attempt has been made to analyse the spatial transport pattern of road based mass transport connectivity using different measures of connectivity.

Key Words: Connectivity, Accessibility, Vehicles flow, Nodes, Spatial Transport Pattern, Transport network

Introduction

We know that the role of transport is very vital in the economic development of any region. Dakshin Dinajpur is one of the backward districts of West Bengal in terms of road length, rail connectivity, industrialisation etc. One of the important factors affecting backwardness of this small district is underdeveloped transportation and communication system. Due to the lack of other modes of transportation system, the road transport system is dominant here. Rail connectivity started in 2004 with the opening of Eklakhi- Balurghat broad gauge line. There is lack of long distance trains from Balurghat Station. Air transportation system is very poor. Weekly helicopter service is available

* *Associate Professor, Department of Geography, University of Gour Banga, Malda, West Bengal*

between Kolkata and Balurghat which is not regular. As a result, highly dominated and centralised road based mass transport services of this district help in the development of the local linkages system. Various quantitative techniques have been used to find out spatial variations in road transportation system in Dakshin Dinajpur district. Important reason behind selection this district for the study is that it shares international boundary with Bangladesh and Hilli is recognised international check-post between India and Bangladesh. So, developed transportation system may take an important role in trade and commerce and travelling for daily passenger.

* *Associate Professor, Department of Geography, University of Gour Banga, Malda, West Bengal.*

Location of the Study Area

The West Dinajpur District was bifurcated into Uttar Dinajpur and Dakshin Dinajpur on 1st April, 1992. The district is situated between 26°35'15" N to 25°10'55"N latitude and 89°0'30" E to 87°48'37"E longitudes. Balurghat is the District Headquarter of Dakshin Dinajpur District. Balurghat is surrounded by other three blocks of this district Kumarganj, Tapan and Hilli in North, West and East Side and on southern side neighbouring country Bangladesh is situated. It has an area of 370.27 Sq. Km.

Source: ddinajpur.nic.in

Objectives

The basic objectives of this study were:

1. To study the present form of transport network of Dakshin Dinajpur District.
2. To examine the connectivity, by the calculation of Alfa, Beta, Gamma index, Detour Index, Shimbel Index and Cyclomatic Number of Dakshin Dinajpur District.
3. To assess the accessibility & Centrality of nodes in present transport network system in Dakshin Dinajpur.

Methodology

The following methodologies have been used for this study:

$$(i) \text{ Alpha Index } (a) = \frac{a-(n-1)}{2n-5}$$

$$(ii) \text{ Beta Index } (a) = \frac{a}{n} \{ \text{Wher, arcs, } n - \text{ nodes} \}$$

$$(iii) \text{ Gamma Index } (y) = \frac{9}{3(n-2)}$$

$$(iv) \text{ Cyclomatic Number} = a-(n - 1)$$

$$(v) \text{ Shimbel Index} = \sum_{i=1}^n d_{ij}$$

$$(vi) \text{ koeing Number } e(x) = \text{MaxyEx}$$

{Wher, d_{ij} = Distance between 'i' and 'j', Maxy Ex = Maximum no. of link}

$$(vii) \text{ Interactive Detour Index} = \frac{\sum \text{ of DI}}{\text{No. of nodes}}$$

$$DI = \frac{AD}{SD} \times 100 \{ \text{Wher, DI} = \text{Dctour Index, AD} = \text{Actual distance among the nodes} \\ \& \text{SD} = \text{Straight distance among the nodes} \}$$

$$(viii) I_G = \frac{\sum d_{ij}}{N} \{ \text{Where, } I_G = \text{Average shortest path length, } d_{ij} = \text{Shortest path lenth} \\ \text{between 'i' and 'j', } N = \text{No. of nodes} \}$$

Sources of Data

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected from the daily passengers/travellers while the secondary data have been collected from State Transport Corporation (STC), Dakshin Dinajpur Bus Syndicate and Mini Bus Organizations and RTO office of Dakshin Dinajpur.

An overview of transport services of Dakshin Dinajpur District

Among the various urban parameters of Dakshin Dinajpur District, one of the most significant is its transport network system which includes rail, road and air ways. Although it shows somewhat a balanced transport network system in the urban perimeter but the interior rural parts are deprived especially in the access to and frequency of transport services. Brief information is given below regarding the major transport systems of Howrah to assess the role of road transport services in the multi modal transport system of this district.

Land Transport System

Among the multimodal transport system of Dakshin Dinajpur district, road based transport services are most suitable for the daily urban and rural passenger movement. In the daily life of Dakshin Dinajpur, the significance of bus, auto-rickshaws and trekker services as the cheapest mode for common rural and urban dwellers cannot be ignored.

Land Transport System

Among the multimodal transport system of Dakshin Dinajpur district, road based transport services are most suitable for the daily urban and rural passenger movement. In the daily life of Dakshin Dinajpur, the significance of bus, auto-rickshaws and trekker services as the cheapest mode for common rural and urban dwellers cannot be ignored.

Fig: 2 Road Transportation System of Dakshin Dinajpur

Source: ddinajpur.nic.in

Results and Analysis

Connectivity analysis (After Kanskey, 1963)

$$\text{Alpha Index (a)} = \frac{58 - (47 - 1)}{(2 \times 47) - 5}$$

$$= 0.13$$

$$\text{Beta Index (B)} = \frac{58}{47}$$

$$= 1.23$$

$$\text{Gamma Index (y)} = \frac{58}{3(47-2)}$$

$$= 0.43$$

$$\text{Cyclomatic Number} = 58 - (47 - 1)$$

$$= 12$$

Alpha Index, Beta Index, Gamma Index & Cyclomatic Number all these are indices of measuring connectivity of transport of a particular area. Except Beta Index all indices are showing low connectivity of transport network in Dakshin Dinajpur District.

*Fig.- 3: Direct connectivity among different nodes
Source: ddinajpur.nic.in*

Table-1: Direct connectivity among different nodes of Dakshin Dinajpur District

Direct Connectivity value	Name of Nodes
1(Very Low Connectivity)	Barihatta, Deul II, Sirshi, Ganguriya II, Rampara, Bashuriya II, Samjhiya, Jakhirpur II, Batun II, Chandipur II, Bhatpara, Autina II, Ganguraya III, Chenchara, HiliCheakpost, Chingishpur
2 (Low Connectivity)	Shibpur, Bansihari, Ganguriya, Alcha,
3 (Moderate Connectivity)	Hili, Chalkvigu, Batun, Jalghar, Jakhirpur, Safanagor, Asokegram, Rampur, Chandipur, Autina, Gofa naghat, Nandanpur, Mahabari, Pundari, Moligoan, Harirampur
4 (High Connectivity)	Balurghat, Kamarpara, Patiram, Kumarjanj, Dwipkhanda, Hajaratpur, Gangarampur, Kushmundi, Pundari II, Bagichapur, Tapan

It is one of the important methods to identify connectivity appearance among different node. Here higher the value indicates higher the connectivity on the other hand lower the value indicates lower the connectivity. From the analysis it is shown that 21 nodes are suffering low connectivity, 16 nodes are faces on moderate connectivity and 10 nodes are belongs in higher connectivity.

Accessibility and Centrality analysis

Accessibility one of the important attributes of a transportation network related to the accessibility and the geographer is particularly concerned with accessibility as a locational feature. Fig.-4 shows the accessibility of different nodes in Dakshin inajpur district. Lower values represent higher accessibility and on the other hand the higher values represents lower accessibility of nodes.

Table 2: Shimbel Values Showing the Accessibility of Dakshin Dinajpur District

Node	Shimble Value	Node	Shimble Value
Balurghat	218	Moligoan	238
Kamarpara	257	Kushmundi	256
Hilli	270	Harirampur	314
Chalkvigu	250	Ganguriya	317
Patiram	195	Barihatta	356
Batun	231	Alcha	276
Jalghar	258	Deul II	297
Kumarjanj	228	Sirshi	358
Jakhipur	332	Ganguriya II	357
Safanagor	234	Rampara	281
Asokegram	216	Basuriya II	258
Rampur	179	Samjhiya	314
Tapan	238	Jakhipur II	298
Dwipkhanda	208	Batun II	276
Chandipur	244	Chandipur II	284
Autina	271	Bhatpara	283
Gofanaghat	237	Autina II	311
Hajaratpur	209	Ganguriya III	330
Gangrapur	179	Chenchara	235
Nandanpur	190	Pundari II	317
Shibpur	203	Bagichapur	280
Bansihari	220	Hili cheakpost	314
Mahabari	249	Chingishpur	305
Pundari	282		

Fig.-4: Accessibility Map of D.Dinajpur

Source: ddinajpur.nic.in

Central location of a transport network system can easily be identified by Koenig Number method. This method implies lower the value indicates centrality and higher the value indicates far away from centrality location. Here in Dakshin Dinajpur district transport Network system, Gangarampur (7), Shibpur (8), Nandanpur (6), Bansihari (8), Chenchara blocks have been identified as on central location because those nodes represents minimum Koenig value than other node in Dakshin Dinajpur District.

Fig 5: Centrality analyses through Koeing Number

Analysis of Relative importance of nodes on the basis of Detour Index

Table 3: Interactive Detour Index showing the rationality in Dakshin Dinajpur District.

NODE	CDI*	MDI**	NODE	CDI	MDI
Balurghat	4861.74	103.44	Moligoan	6902.60	146.86
Kamarpara	6372.35	135.58	Kushmundi	6467.60	137.61
Hilli	6128.69	130.40	Harirampur	5613.06	119.43
Chalkvigu	5729.64	121.91	Ganguriya	6020.81	128.10
Patiram	5954.50	126.69	Barihatta	6448.16	137.19
Batun	6070.09	129.15	Alcha	6510.65	138.52
Jalghar	6407.23	136.32	Deul II	6553.85	139.44
Kumarjanj	6873.86	146.25	Sirshi	6403.63	136.25

Jakhirpur	6324.24	134.56	Ganguriya II	6225.32	132.45
Safanagor	7845.03	166.92	Rampara	7167.21	152.49
Asokegram	5739.11	122.11	Basuriya II	6621.35	140.88
Rampur	5789.79	123.19	Samjhiya	6950.57	147.88
Tapan	6398.71	136.14	Jakhirpur II	7386.05	157.15
Dwipkhanda	6458.64	137.42	Batun II	6822.15	145.15
Chandipur	6664.77	141.80	Chandipur II	9252.44	196.86
Autina	7887.06	167.81	Bhatpara	5756.91	122.49
Gofanaghat	6581.27	140.03	Autina II	6527.62	138.89
Hajaratpur	6092.90	129.64	Ganguriya III	7510.62	159.80
Gangrampur	5650.21	120.22	Chenchara	7701.71	163.87
Nandanpur	5756.35	122.48	Pundari II	7412.57	157.71
Shibpur	5416.90	115.25	Bagichapur	5591.51	118.97
Bansihari	5552.23	118.13	Hili check-post	6999.99	148.94
Mahabari	5439.61	115.74	Chingishpur	6234.20	132.64
Pundari	6866.45	146.09			

*CDI- Composite Detour Index

**MDI- Mean Detour Index

Fig.6: Relative Importance of Nodes through Detour Index
 Source: ddinajpur.nic.in

Analysis of Shortest Path Matrix

Table 4: Shortest Path Lengths showing the Efficiency of Nodes in Dakshin Dinajpur

Node	Average Shortest path length(Km)	Node	Average Shortest path length(Km)
Balurghat	41.85	Moligoan	44.88
Kamarpara	46.49	Kushmundi	48.04
Hilli	54.13	Harirampur	45.39
Chalkvigu	39.22	Ganguriya	42.58
Patiram	36.06	Barihatta	51.45
Batun	37.97	Alcha	53.23
Jalghar	41.12	Deul II	52.89
Kumarjanj	44.39	Sirshi	51.10
Jakhipur	43.28	Ganguriya II	44.88
Safanagor	50.29	Rampara	49.60
Asokegram	36.07	Basuriya II	40.88
Rampur	29.97	Samjhiya	53.70
Tapan	33.83	Jakhipur II	51.39
Dwipkhanda	33.73	Batun II	45.76
Chandipur	37.90	Chandipur II	53.90
Autina	47.02	Bhatpara	45.95
Gofanaghat	36.08	Autina II	40.77
Hajaratpur	32.72	Ganguriya III	46.66
Gangrampur	30.08	Chenchara	41.63
Nandanpur	32.61	Pundari II	52.76
Shibpur	32.78	Bagichapur	40.19
Bansihari	33.37	Hili Checkpost	59.91
Mahabari	35.26	Chingishpur	59.48
Pundari	39.54		

Fig. 7: Average Shortest path length

Average shortest path length shows the efficiency of different nodes in Dakshin Dinajpur District. From the above table and diagram it is observed that Patiram, Tapan, Gangarampur, Shibpur, Mahabari, Bansihari, is higher efficiency nodes on the other hand Balurghat, Patiram, Jalghar, etc. nodes are moderate efficiency nodes and excepting of higher and moderate efficiency nodes all the nodes belongs in lower efficiency nodes.

**Analysis of Maximum vehicles flow
Bus services in Dakshin Dinajpur**

Bus is the prime mode for mainly short distance and sometimes long distance mass transport services for the people of Dakshin Dinajpur. On the basis of trip generation and destination system, the bus services of Dakshin Dinajpur can be categorized into two different types:

- a) Within Dakshin Dinajpur Bus Services,
- b) Dakshin Dinajpur to Long distance bus services

(a) Within Dakshin Dinajpur Bus Services

Traffic flow diagram shows the flow of vehicles from one node to another node. Maximum width represents maximum vehicles flow; on the other hand minimum width represents minimum vehicles flow. From the above Balurghat to Bansihari and Balurghat to Hilli shows maximum vehicles flow and Balurghat to Tapan Road suffering in a minimum vehicles flow.

Fig.8: Traffic Flow Diagram

Source: ddinajpur.nic.in

(b) Dakshin Dinajpur to Long Distance bus services

Table: 5 Vehicles flow from Dakshin Dinajpur per day

Vehicles Flow from Dakshin Dinajpur	Total no. permitted bus
Dakshin Dinajpur to Malda	34
Dakshin Dinajpur to Kolkatta	13
Dakshin Dinajpur to Siliguri	17
Dakshin dinajpur to Bardhwan	4
Dakshin Dinajpur to Uttar Dinajpur	24

Source: RTO, D. Dinajpur (2016)

Fig.9: Flow of Permitted bus from Dakshin Dinajpur Head Quarter

Flow diagram shows the maximum flow of permitted buses from Dakshin Dinajpur to other long distance bus station like Kolkatta, Siliguri, Malda, Uttar Dinajpur etc. The maximum flow of buses has been shown from Dakshin Dinajpur to Malda and Uttar Dinajpur (34, 24). A minimum no. of buses flows from Dakshin Dinajpur to Bardhwan that is 9. Siliguri bus station receives 17 no. of buses from Dakshin Dinajpur.

Table 6: Minimum Ticket Price and Required Time of Different Transport Modes from Balurghat (Dakshin Dinajpur) to Kolkatta.

Types of Transport Mode	Minimum Ticket Price	Required Time (Hour)
Helicopter	1500	2
Train	155	8
Bus	330	12

Fig.10: Comparison between among different modes of transport

Although the helicopter service is time saving but from the passengers view only for the high price of ticket they can't travel by helicopter. The helicopter files without passenger or very minimum passenger from the Balurghat airport.

Major findings

- a) The pattern of connectivity of Dakshin Dinajpur District is not so well.
- b) Balurghat is the main nodal point of Dakshin Dinajpur District and has the high connectivity and In case of direct connectivity, and from which the direct connectivity gradually decreases.
- c) Accessibility is more in some of the node of NH512, Such as Balurghat, Patiram, Gangarampur, Bansihari etc.
- d) In the study of centrality, It is found that Gangarampur, Shibpur, Nandanpur, Bansihari blocks have been identified as on central location.
- e) In terms of rationality analysis it is again found that Balurghat, Gangarampur, Shibpur, Nandanpur, Bansihari blocks are highly rational or engage with high accessibility.
- f) Tapan, Gangarampur, Shibpur, Mahabari, Bansihari, is higher efficiency nodes on the other hand Balurghat, Patiram, Jalghar, etc. nodes are moderate efficiency nodes and excepting of higher and moderate efficiency nodes all the nodes belongs in lower efficiency nodes which is identified by average shortest-path matrix.
- g) Maximum vehicles pressure has been seen on NH512 and low vehicles pressure has been seen on some pocket route of Dakshin Dinajpur District.

Conclusion

Emergency response planning must include effective management of transportation resources, including public transit services. Failure to do this often leads to significant problems and risks, resulting in huge costs to society. This study shows that although some cities and transit agencies have made sincere efforts to address these problems, there is an overall lack of guidance and resources for practitioners. Research should be shared with transportation and emergency planners, transit agencies and decision-makers to direct the formation of these guidelines. If you plan cities for cars and traffic, you get cars and traffic. If you plan for people and places, you get people and places.

References

- Arora, N.L. (2003). *A Text book of Transportation Engineering*. New India Publishing House. New Delhi
- Bhaduri, Sukla (2003). "*Mass Transport Services in Calcutta Metropolitan Area*", Vaidya Publishing House.
- Black, W. R. (2003). *Transportation a Geographical Analysis*. Guilford Press. New York
- Farris, M.T. & Harding, F.E., (1976). *Passenger Transportation..* Prentice-Hall. USA
- Gautam, P.S. (1992). *Transport Geography of India*. Mittal Publication. New Delhi.
- Halder, D. K. ed. (2007). "*Studies in Urban Transport*", Book well Publishers, New Delhi.
- Halder, D. K. ed. (2002). "*Urban Transport Pricing and Planning*", Allied Publishers Limited, Kolkata.
- Hanson, S., and Genevieve, G. Eds. (2004). *The Geography of Urban Transportation*. New York. The Guilford Press.
- Kansky, K.J. (1963). *Structure of transportation Networks: Relation between Network Geometry and regional characteristics*. University of Chicago. Department of Geography. Research papers no.84
- Munshi, Sunil Kumar (1980). *Geography of Transportation in Eastern India under the British Raj*, Calcutta

Role of Neo humanist School in Moral Development of Children at Primary Level- A Case Study

Mrs. Sunandita Bhowmik *

Dr. Ramakanta Mohalik **

Abstract

This study deals with different aspects of morality in Neohumanist school. The study also highlights the students' ability of moral judgment. The concept of morality developed in students' mind at primary level are also explored in this study. The study also reveals how children develop their higher mind through activities and reflective practices. The study focuses on the role of Neohumanist School in enhancing morality among children. Observation, interview, reasoning for moral dilemma and bibliotherapy are used to collect data. The study finds that harmony with self and harmony with others, universal love, sense of Omnipotent's presence, service spirit, social welfare and desire for collective good are the main basis of moral development of children. The principles of harmony and universal love are embedded in curriculum both as content and as practice. The students avoid such actions and thoughts that cause harm to others even if these bring self pleasure.

Key words: *Neo-humanism, Neo-humanist School, Morality, Harmony, Universal love*

Introduction

Human existence is based on morality. Morality builds the foundation of education at the primary level. Moral standards are deficient today and are lacking in the present educational system. Human being with high moral strength is able to take wise decision throughout the life. Therefore, morality plays an important role in education system at primary level. In Neo-humanist education, the place of morality is widened. Children regularly practice ten moral principles specified by Neo humanism philosophy. As a result of which children develop some positive characters which ultimately become permanent traits of personality in adulthood. The teachers possess high moral characters. Through interaction with teachers, peers and school environment, children establish a firm foundation of values and ethics. Neo-humanist values are cultivated in schools at every step, focusing on the personal development of the child. Practice of morality are the most important subject in the syllabus at primary levels in Neo-humanist school.

Neo-humanism

* *Research Scholar, RIE, (NCERT), Bhubaneswar.*

** *Associate Professor in Education, Regional Institute of Education, (NCERT), Bhubaneswar*

In 1982, the Indian philosopher P.R.Sarkar(1921-1990) has described Humanism in a new way- “practice of love for all creation including plants, animals and the inanimate world”. This is Neo-humanism- a psycho-spiritual philosophy. Neo-humanism is a reinterpretation of Humanism. It takes the universal aspiration of Humanism, to reach beyond the limitation of humanity and strive for unity at the social level, and suggests a universalism that includes all animate and inanimate existence. Morality, humanity, rationality and above all spirituality are the important aspects of Neo-humanism.

Neo-humanist School

These schools are based on the philosophy of Neo Humanism and run successfully across the country for last three decades. Most of the schools are at primary level means from 3+ age group to 9+ age group. The schools are the places where the values of Neo-humanism can be realized. At the primary level, the schools follow their autonomous board named Ananda Marga Gurukul which is located in Kolkata and are controlled by the special branch of Ananda Marga called Education, Relief and Welfare Section(ERAWS,1963).Near about one thousand schools are there in India, most of which are at primary level. Ananda Marga schools are there in 180 countries across the world. The ultimate goal of these schools is to awaken the divine consciousness that is hidden inside the child. In West Bengal, there are near about 130 primary schools which run in the name of Ananda Marga Primary Schools. Most of the schools are headed by Swamiji (monk) who are trained in Neo-humanism philosophy. The environment of Ananda Marga Schools maintains a balance in the individual and social needs of children. The environment is physically safe, emotionally secure and psychologically enabling.

Morality

In Neo-humanist education, morality means harmony with self and harmony with others. Neo-humanism defines ten moral principles. These include: non harming, benevolent truthfulness, non stealing, universal love, simple living, cleanliness of body and mind, contentment, social service, inspirational study, self knowledge and spiritual pursuit. Morality leads to a sense of universalism and pervasive sense of love and compassion for all creation (Sarkar,P.R 1981). Morality has both an intellectual and an impulsive aspect. Through moral development children must learn what is right and what is wrong. Children must develop a desire to do what is right, to act for the common good (E. B.Hurlock 1978).

Harmony

The universal cardinal human values oriented towards creating mental harmony. It defines one's role to the society and one's personal integration. Application of these values transcends a dos and don'ts mentally, leading to a sense of love and compassion for all creation (Avk. Anandarama and A. Brim 2010).

Universal Love

The feeling of interconnectedness of self with all living and non living things. At the core of this thought is spirituality. In order to realize the essence of spirituality regular practice of meditation is considered to be the main tool in NHE school. The concept of omnipotent is deeply embedded in the entire curriculum. Trying to see and love the Infinite Consciousness that is manifested in everything around us.

Needs of the Study

Moral development is neglected in our present educational system. As a result of which so called educational institutions produce only talented students with competitive mentality. Students, now a days are motivated by self pleasure or "*AtmaSukha Tattva*". Concept of true morality is totally missing in them. As the primary education lays the foundation of an individual, hence moral development must be given importance in primary curriculum. The work of Glueck, E.T (1966) on reasons of juvenile delinquency has found that a continuation of pattern of unsocial behavior that had its origin in childhood is the root cause of juvenile delinquency. Today, studies of moral development have become one of the focal points of psychological research. Only a book of moral education is not sufficient to moral development of children. It needs regular practice of good habits, regular interaction with adults who possess high moral characters in school. Regular practice will give them moral insight. Shambhushivananda, Ac (2011) critically analyzed the role of morality in order to maintain harmony. He suggested the yoga and meditation based Neohumanist education is essential to remove the dichotomy that exists between me and them. Devajinana (2011) found that morality, if practiced through a conscious act of living then it creates a dynamic force where no desire is left for theft; and all tendencies of falsehood disappear. Palenda, A and Santos, L.P(2011) found that Neo-humanist school creates an environment where aggressive attitudes in children are eased and interpersonal relationships are favored, then the children become benevolent with all beings that surround them. Jordon(2013) critically analyzed the role of Neo-humanist school in Conflict

resolution of students.

From above discussions, it is clear that moral intervention is essential part in childhood. School curriculum has great influence on moral development of children. Neo-humanist school follows ten universal moral principles in school curriculum both as content and practice. In order to know the concept of morality of students at primary level and different activities that school follow to enhance morality the present study is required. No empirical study has been done in this field.

Objectives

1. To study different aspects of morality in Neo humanist school.
2. To study the extent to which the concept of morality develops in students
3. To explore the ability of moral judgment of students
4. To study the role of Neo-humanist school in enhancing morality among the students.

Methodology

It was a case study of Neo-humanist School (Ananda Marga School) located in Siliguri, West Bengal. Grade 4 students are treated as sample.

Tools and Techniques

In order to achieve the first objective which is to study different aspects of morality in Neo humanist school, content analysis of NHE curriculum was done. Observation and semi structured interview were conducted to achieve the second and fourth objectives. Moral dilemma and bibliotherapy were used to explore the moral judgment ability of students.

Analysis and Interpretation

Different aspects of morality

Some noticeable traits found in children are positive views of life, optimism, desire for collective good, and ability to analyze logically. All these values are reflected in their thoughts and actions. What activities a child doing is not important, but how these activities are conducted and with what spirit are the most important factor. It reflects the inner sense of morality.

The ten universal moral values implicit in Neo-humanism are(A, Annandarama and B, Arete 2010)

Sl.No.	Moral Principles	Expected traits to be developed
1.	Non Harming	Friendliness, caring, kindness, compassion, gentleness
2.	Benevolent Truth	Respect, honesty, moral courage, straightforwardness
3.	Non Stealing	Generosity, trustworthiness, integrity, fairness, justice
4.	Universal Love	Appreciation, unity, reflection, joy, sweetness
5.	Moderation	Empathy, cooperation, responsibility, leadership
6.	Cleanliness	Smartness, etiquette, introspection, sincerity, self discipline
7.	Contentment	Positive outlook, forgiveness ,tolerance .self confidence
8.	Sacrifice	Selfless service, humility ,initiative, duty
9.	Wisdom Study	Rationality, expansion of mind, self-knowledge, wisdom
10.	Cosmic Shelter	Meditation, concentration ,reverence, love, bliss

The children in Neo humanist school regularly practice these universal moral principles . The ethics and values related with moral principles are reflected in the curriculum. The stories, poems rhymes, songs of content speak about compassion, honesty, cooperation; sharing .The school is mainly based on the combination of Idealism and Pragmatism. That means let the child realizing the essence of Idealism through regular practice and experience. Along with the intellectual development, this school tries to strengthen psychic power and intuitional and transcendental knowledge. In order to develop inner conscience, the curriculum incorporates Yoga for health, quiet time exercise, moral teaching, morning circle and control of breathing, music, dance, drama, service projects etc.

Neo-humanist curriculum mainly covers two broad aspects of morality: harmony with others and harmony with self. The concept of harmony is the basis for morality.

Concept of morality developed among students

The main concept of morality develops in students is discrimination between good and bad. Another noticeable value aspect found in students is service spirit. Most of the students are aware of the fact that giving something to anybody brings happiness. Selfless service is at the core of the curriculum both as content and as practice. The students have a firm basis of right and wrong concept. The actions and thoughts that may cause harm to anybody are wrong and hence students avoid all such deeds. For example, when a class three boy was asked to take out a crayon from his friend's bag, the boy replied, "let me ask my friend" and he rushed to the playground to take permission. Students also develop logical mind. For example, a class

four girl told maths teacher as one of their favorite teachers although he scolds them when they commit any mistake.

The Ability of Moral Judgment of Students

The moral judgment scores of students improved following an intervention in which they discussed moral dilemmas under the direction of an adult facilitator who stimulated their thinking by means of Socratic questioning (Blatt & Kohlberg, 1975). Subsequent research indicated that these developmental advances can be achieved on a regular basis (Lockwood, 1978; Schlaefli, Rest, & Thoma, 1985).

In order to explore the reasoning ability of the students, following activities were done.

Activity 1 :Moral Dilemmas

Moral dilemmas, which focuses on hypothetical moral questions and invites students to resolve situations according to their own personal perspectives, philosophies and values. Although the ability of moral judgment depends on intellectual ability yet the influence of environment is also immense. The students of class 4 were encountered with some hypothetical cases related with daily life problems like stealing, lying, causing harm to others, spoiling others for self pleasure etc. It has been found that students are aware of good-bad and right-wrong concept. The underlying reason of this concept is sense of benevolence and welfare. Children's high level of reasoning, fund of information, critical sensitivity and high sense of ethics and values enable them to analyze moral dilemmas in a desirable way.

For example, one person needs a costly medicine to save his wife's life. Doctor has prescribed to provide this medicine within 24 hours. But the person failed to collect money within this period of time. He requested the shopkeeper to provide him that medicine with fewer amounts. But the shopkeeper denied to give .The person broke the medical store and stole that medicine. Did he do right? Most of the students said that the person committed mistake. The reasons they provided are: (1) Stealing is bad (2) Causing harm to anybody by action or thought is also wrong. The person has broken the medical store and thus causing harm to the shopkeeper. So he has committed mistake.

Activity 2: Bibliotherapy

Students were allowed to read some moral stories and were given the opportunities to examine moral and spiritual values. Students identified the best moral character and have explained the reason why did they choose the character. Most of the children have chosen their hero who were kind, showed

mercy to others, helped the poor and those who fought against ghost or demons.

There are four moral values found in students' moral reasoning which enable them to thought and behave morally: a) Avoiding doing harm to anybody with words, thoughts or actions. b) Avoiding the exploitation of others c) Not motivated always for selfish pleasure and most importantly, d) The sense of Omnipotent's presence everywhere

Role of Neo-humanist School in Enhancing Morality Among Students

Stu-Vol or Students Voluteer

Stu-vol is one of the subjects of Neo-humanist curriculum that is taught from nursery to std.V. Stu-vol is designed to bring Neo-humanist values into the entire learning of the class. Stu-vol is the unique feature of NHE curriculum. Morality is one of the important aspects of stu-vol. This special class was often taken by the monk or nun of the school. Through various activities in Stu-vol class, students could realize their role in functioning, contributing, sharing, cooperating and other social activities. The Neo humanist school teachers discuss and demonstrate the following aspects of moral values: helping others get their needs met, loving unconditionally, asking for support, removing internal impurities such as greed, hatred and pride. Adult guided and supervised activities such as role playing, drama, mono act, dance drama that speak about moral values help in internalizing these values.

Service Project

Selfless service is at the core of Neo-humanist curriculum. Different activities related with service spirit are carried out in school. Students learn the truth that serving others brings happiness. Schools are involved in various relief work, community services, free medical camp etc. The teachers always encourage sharing belongings of students, cooperating each other in many activities.

Developing Rationalistic Mentality

The curriculum of NHE is framed in such a way that the noble aspects of a child are explored. The child realizes that animals also experience pleasure and pain. Even the inanimate things have minds which is in dormant stage. Children start realizing a fine linking thread among all creature living and non-living. Rationalistic mind which is the main approach of Neo-humanism helps the children to realize the sense of duty and higher level of understanding that they should be sympathetic to all living beings. Children are not allowed to do whatever they think good, rather NHE cultivates moral judgment in such a way that before executing any action they should think whether it is conducive to

human welfare, whether it is for the benefit and happiness of all beings. Moral development is characterized by a growing commitment to personal rules and values which become part of the individual's identity (Eisenberg, 1986). This sort of internalization naturally leads to moral behavior in a wide range of situations.

Teachers' Strength of Character

Teachers of Neo-humanist School possess high moral character. The role of teacher is significant in Neo-humanist education. They are physically fit, morally sound and spiritually elevated. Students learn from teachers while interacting with them and imitating them. Mental purity is reflected through their conduct. Teachers providing emotional support inside and outside the classroom help them to tie a strong emotional bonding with the students. Through every action, teachers demonstrated their personal commitment to character development. In order to empower students to internalize a greater sense of morality, teachers are constantly upgrading their own moral structure and integrity.

Major Findings

1. Some of the valuable moral aspects found in Neo-humanist school children are: Non Harming, Benevolent truth, Non Stealing, Universal love, Moderation, Mental and physical cleanliness, service spirit, Wisdom study and Cosmic Shelter.
2. The study has shown that regular practice of moral principles in schools help in developing conscience and higher mind of the students. The moral concept developed in students are:
 - a) Avoiding doing harm to anybody with words, thoughts or actions.
 - b) Avoiding the exploitation of others
 - c) Not motivated always for selfish pleasure and most importantly,
 - d) The sense of Omnipotent's presence everywhere
3. Neo-humanist school has significant role in developing rational and logical mind of the students which in turn help students in reasoning of moral dilemmas and taking wise decision for the welfare of the society.
4. Through direct teaching and identification students can learn the internal control of individual's behavior.
5. Early intervention of moral development among primary children in Neo-humanist school has

built a firm base of morality where the children internalize the value of desire for collective good which initiates inner transformation.

Educational Implications

1. The primary curriculum needs to be reviewed and must incorporate morality both as content and as practice. The present curriculum is overloaded with skill and knowledge oriented content. Practice of morality is almost missing in school. Through regular practice of ten moral principles students have developed moral insight.
2. Students must observe some dos and don'ts in school at their early age. They are expected to develop a scale of values and a conscience to guide them when they must make a moral decision.
3. This study has implication in teachers' role in enhancing moral development among students. Teacher education programme should be re oriented towards developing morality. Teachers' conduct and strength of character should reflect high moral values.
4. The study has given the present status of true morality of students of Neo-humanist school. Therefore, the Neo-humanist curriculum of moral development must be incorporated in primary level curriculum.

References

- Anandarama. Brim, A(2010). Foundations of Neohumanist education: Philosophy, principles, practice. Ananda Marga Gurukul Publication.Ithaca, NY.USA.
- Ananda Mitra Avtk, Ac.(1991). Ethics for a new humanity.AMPS:Kolkata
- Ananda Nivedita Avtk, Ac(1999), Teach me to fly, Gurukul publication, Kolkata
- Beaty, Janice J.(2002) Observing Development of the Young Child.Upper Saddle River, NJ:Merrill Prentiss Hall.
- Blatt, M., & Kohlberg, L. (1975). The effects of classroom discussion upon children's level of moral judgment. Journal of Moral Education, 4, 129-161.
- Devajinana, Ac(2011). Moral Foundation of Society.)GN: Issue-32.USA. Ithaca.
- Eisenberg, N. (1986). Altruistic emotion, cognition, and behavior. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum
- Glueck,E.T(1966). A more discriminative instrument for the identification of potential delinquents. Journal of criminal law 57. 27-30.
- Hendrick,J(1988). The Whole Child. Columbus, Ohio: Merrill Publishing Company
- Hurlock,E.B(1978). Child Development. Sixth Edition.Mc Graw Hill Education Pvt

- Ltd.Jordon,S(2013).Conflict resolution in Neohumanist school. GN:36 USA.
- Lockwood, A. (1978). Effects of values clarification and moral development curricula on schoolage subjects. A critical review of recent research. Review of Education Research, 48, 325-364.
- Marcus, B.(2012).Finding Relationship as a Base for NeoHumanist Classroom Practice. Gurukul Network. New York.
- Naksamrit,J(2013)The less amount of Side Based Alternative: Neohumanist school.Issue 36. Pp27. Ithaca USA.
- Sarkar, P. R(1981). Liberation of Intellect and Neohumanism. Kolkata.
- Shambhushivananda, Ac (2011). Global Peace: Role of Harmony.GN:32.USA
- Taylor, Barbara,J(1985). A Child Goes Forth.New York: Mc Millan Publishing Company.
- Pelanda, A. Andressa., and Santos P. Liana.(2011).Circle of love : An Instrument to helpChildhood Development. Brazil.
- Walene, J(1977). Handbook for Educating in the New Age.USA:A.R.E Press.

An Interactional Study of Academic Anxiety in Relation to Gender and School Type among Secondary School Students

*Magdolyn Karthak**

Abstract

Anxiety is an age old concept which has been the subject of debate among philosophers. Every human being experiences anxiety in day to day life. The term “anxiety” has been used in different situation with different interpretation. Modern civilization with its highly developed technology has rightly been termed as the age of anxiety. There is hardly an individual who has not experienced moments of anxiety in his life its symptoms are extremely common in childhood and adolescence, and can negatively interfere with well-being, social life, academic performance, and development of social skill. Therefore the present study was to find out the extent academic anxiety among students in relation to gender and school type 120 students were selected randomly from different government and private schools of Gangtok city, Sikkim. The tool that was used in study were Academic Anxiety Scale for Children (AASC) tool developed by A.K and Dr. A. Sen Gupta (2013) and personal data blank constructed by the researcher. The result have indicated no significant difference in the academic anxiety in students in relation to type of management and gender.

Key Words: *Interaction Analysis, Academic Anxiety, Gender, School Type.*

Introduction

The term “anxiety” has been used in different situation with different interpretation. Modern civilization with its highly developed technology has rightly been termed as the age of anxiety. There is hardly an individual who has not experienced moments of anxiety in his life its symptoms are extremely common in childhood and adolescence, and can negatively interfere with well-being, social life, academic performance, and development of social skill. Anxiety is not the same as fear, which is a response to a real or perceived immediate threat, whereas anxiety is the expectation of future threat. Anxiety is a feeling of fear, worry and, uneasiness, usually generalized and unfocused as an overreaction to a situation that is only subjectively seen as menacing. It is often accompanied by muscular tension, restlessness, fatigue and problems in concentration. Anxiety can be appropriate, but when experienced regularly the individual may suffer from an anxiety disorder. People facing

* *Assistant Professor, Harkamaya College of Education, Samdur, Tadong-73702, Gangtok.,
email id: lepachmagdolyn26@gmail.com*

anxiety may withdraw from situations which have provoked anxiety in the past.

Anxiety can be either a short term 'state' or a long term 'trait'; State Anxiety describes the experience of unpleasant feelings when confronted with specific situations, demands or a particular object or event. State anxiety arises when the person makes a mental assessment of some type of threat.

When the object or situation that is perceived as threatening goes away, the person no longer experiences anxiety. Trait anxiety refers to the differences between people in terms of their tendency to experience state anxiety in response to the anticipation of a threat. People with a high level of trait anxiety experience more intense degrees of state anxiety to specific situations than most people do and experience anxiety toward a broader range of situations or objects than most people.

Academic anxiety is a normal response to the pressure of school related to teachers, certain subject teachers like mathematics, English etc. It can help motivate students to study for tests or complete assignments, sometimes the anxiety can reach levels that hinder academic performance. Instead of improvement Some students procrastinate The Studies have revealed that some children appears to perform below their best in situations characterized by a high degree of anxiety It is common occurrence to hear teachers comment that a certain student gets upset that falls to pieces or chokes up during an examination and fails to live up to the promises in the classroom. The student's problems are peculiar to their age. They are also worried about their academic performance. Many students are under great parental pressure to score high marks. In order to cope with problems like this CCE have also suggested ways to reduce stress and anxiety relating to examinations among young students by measuring the performance of the students throughout the year from not only their scholastic but also co scholastic aspects. Therefore the present study was conducted to find out the extent academic anxiety among students and to establish the relation between academic anxiety and achievement of the students.

Review of Literature

Bhansali and Trivedi (2008) performed study on “Is Academic Anxiety Gender Specific: A Comparative Study” A comparative study between boys and girls of 16-18 years was conducted to know the academic anxiety prevailing amongst them. The objective of the study was to find out the gender differences in Academic Anxiety amongst adolescents. Incidental purposive sampling technique was used in the selection of the sample. A total sample of 240 adolescent, 120 boys and 120

girls from different high schools of Jodhpur city were selected. Self-constructed Adolescent Problem Inventory was pilot tested and applied on the chosen sample. The Results revealed that considerable amount of Academic Anxiety prevailed amongst the sample. It was seen that girls on the whole had more incidences and intensity of academic anxiety in comparison to boys.

Deb, Chatterjee, and Wals (2010) performed study on "Anxiety among High School Students in India: Comparisons across Gender, School type, Social Strata and Perceptions of Quality time with Parents" The broad objective of the study was to understand better anxiety among adolescents in Kolkata city, India. Specifically, the study compared anxiety across gender and school type. A group of 460 adolescents (220 boys and 240 girls), aged 13-17 years were recruited to participate in the study via a multi-stage sampling technique. The data were collected using a self-report semi-structured questionnaire and a standardized psychological test, the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory. Results show that anxiety was prevalent in the sample with 20.1% of boys and 17.9% of girls found to be suffering from high anxiety. More boys were anxious than girls.

Latha (2012) conducted study on "A Study of Self Concept and Academic Anxiety among Secondary School Students of Mandya city". The present study aims to assess the self concept and academic anxiety of secondary school students in relation to gender, types of school and standard of study. The study was conducted on sample of 264 secondary school students in Mandya City. The sample was drawn by stratified Random Sampling Technique giving due representation on gender, standard of study and type of institution. The scale used for measuring the self concept for student developed by Dr. Harmohan Singh and Smt. Saraswathi Singh. It has 22 trait descriptive adjectives and followed by five point rating scale Academic Anxiety scale developed by Dr. A. K Singh and Dr.Sengupta.A. Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' test were secondary school. The findings revealed .There exists no significant difference between boys and girls and also government, and private schools in academic anxiety of secondary school students of Mandya City.

Banga (2014) performed a study on "Academic Anxiety among High School Students in Relation to Gender and Type of Family". The study was conducted to study the difference in the academic

anxiety in relation to gender and family type . The sample for present study comprised of 200 all 9th class students of government schools Hamirpur district of Himachal Pradesh. All the students from 8 schools were selected by the researcher in order to realize the objectives of present study. in the present study, academic anxiety scale towards school students of class viii,ix, x (age range: 13-16years) has been developed by Dr.A.k.singh and Dr. A. Sen Gupta (2009) was used. in order to obtain empirical verification of the proposed hypotheses, the data was analyzed by applying t-test. The study revealed that there was no significant gender difference in academic anxiety of high school students.

Atieq and Siddiqui (2014) Performed study on “An Interactional Study of Academic Anxiety in Relation to Socio-economic status, Gender and School type among Secondary School Students”. Some of the objectives of the study were to find out the levels of academic anxiety with respect to school types, gender of secondary school students. 222 students studying in 10th grade of government and private schools of Aligarh city Uttar Pradesh were taken as sample. . The value of the sample was assessed using Academic Anxiety Scale for Children (AASC) developed by A.K. Singh and Dr. A. Sen Gupta and Socio-Economic Status Scale (Rural and Urban) develop by Dr. A.K. Kailia and Dr. S. Sahu was used. The data collected was subjected to statistical analysis by using one sample t- test, three-way ANOVA and Pearson Co- efficient of correlation. Interaction effect does not have significant difference with regard to gender and school type.

Banga (2015) conducted study on “A Study of Academic Anxiety among Private Senior Secondary School Students of Kangra District”. The present study is undertaken with a view to find out the nature of distribution of scores for private senior secondary school boys, girls and total sample on Academic Anxiety variable. In present study the sample was drawn from 05 Private Senior Secondary schools situated in Kangra district of Himachal Pradesh. From each school a sample of 20 students (10 boys and 10 girls) were selected randomly by lottery method. Finally, the total sample consisted of 100(50 boys and 50 girls) students. To collect the requisite data for the present study the investigator used academic anxiety scale for children. Academic Anxiety Scale for children (AASC) by Dr. A.K Singh and Dr. (Ms.) A. Sen Gupta (1986). The finding was that the private senior secondary school students differ in their level of Academic Anxiety.

Rationale of the Study

In today's world, academic anxiety has become one of those predominant issues that students cannot ignore if they want to succeed in school. It leads to problem in concentrating while studying and remembering information while studying and remembering information while completing tests, which makes the student, feel helpless and like a failure. According to Greenfield Community College, although a manageable level of academic anxiety is actually a good thing. Moderate academic anxiety provides the motivation, the students require to exert in completing assigned schoolwork and preparing to take examinations. Without any anxiety most of the students lack the motivation generally to do anything in life. Therefore, moderate level of academic anxiety is essential to motivate students to study for better achievement. (Singh, 2013).

Academic anxiety only becomes a problem that needs a solution when the amount experienced grows so excessive that a student is no longer able to function productively. A high level of anxiety interferes with concentration and affects one's memory. In this way high academic anxiety may be one of the obstacles of academic achievement. If academic anxiety isn't properly addressed, it can have many serious and lasting consequences, such as causing a student to procrastinate, perform poorly in schoolwork, fail classes and withdraw from socializing with peers or pursuing activities that interest him. Therefore it should not be ignored at any cost, if one is really concerned about students' academic performance. If not tackled properly on time it can have serious and far reaching negative implication (Matto and Nabi 2012).

The Studies have revealed that some children appears to perform below their best in situations characterized by a high degree of anxiety It is common occurrence to hear teachers comment that a certain student gets upset that falls to pieces or chokes up during an examination and fails to live up to the promises in the classroom. The student's problems are peculiar to their age. They are also worried about their academic performance. Many students are under great parental pressure to score high marks. In order to cope with problems like this CCE have also suggested ways to reduce stress and anxiety relating to examinations among young students by measuring the performance of the students throughout the year from not only their scholastic but also co scholastic aspects. Therefore the present study was conducted to find out the extent academic anxiety among students and to establish the relation between academic anxiety and achievement of the students. Considering the above issues the following research questions were formulated:

- Is academic anxiety same for all groups of students at secondary level?

- Is there any significant difference in academic anxiety in secondary school students with regard to gender?
- Is there any significant difference in academic anxiety in secondary school students with regard to type of management of school?
- Is there any interaction of gender and type of school management on to academic anxiety?

Statement of the Problem

Thus, the problem of the study was stated as *“An Interactional Study of Academic Anxiety In Relation To Gender and School Type Among Secondary School Students”*.

Objectives

- To study the academic anxiety of students.
- To study the academic anxiety of students in relation to their gender.
- To study out academic anxiety if any in relation to the type of management of the school.
- To study interaction effect of gender and type of school in academic anxiety.

Hypotheses

Ho₁: The level of academic anxiety is not the same for all students.

Ho₂: There will be no significant difference in academic anxiety of all the achievers in relation to their gender.

Ho₃: There will be no significant difference in academic anxiety of all the achievers in relation to the type of management of the school.

Ho₄: There will be no significant interaction effect of gender and type of management on academic anxiety of students.

Methodology and Procedure:

Design of the Study

A survey method was adopted to obtain precise information for a study on the academic anxiety in students at the secondary level of education.

The Design

A normative study of survey type was adopted as the design of the study. An interactional study of Academic Anxiety of students in relation to gender and school type was studied.

Sample

The selection of the sample was done through simple random sampling procedure as the researcher

was bound by time constraints. The researcher had taken 120 samples from 4 different schools from in and around Gangtok city. In this context, the government and non-government schools of East Sikkim have been under the study.

Table 1 Sex and Management wise distribution of the sample

Variation	Sub Samples	Number of Samples
Gender	Boys	60
	Girls	60
Management	Government	60
	Private	60

The Tools

To measure academic anxiety of the secondary school students, Academic Anxiety scale for children (AASC) by Singh and Sen (2013) was used. The scale consisted of 20 items. In academic Anxiety Scale Children, each item of the test is scored as either +1 or 0. There were two items positive and negative. All positive items which were endorsed by subjects as 'yes' and all negative items no 4, 9, 16 and 18 which were endorsed by the subjects as 'no' are given a score of +1. A score of zero is subjected to all other answers. Thus, high score on the test indicates high academic anxiety and low score on the test indicates low academic anxiety.

Personal data bank comprising the following details: Name, Age, Sex, Name of the School, Standard.

Result and Discussion

The techniques of data analysis included both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive measures were used to compute the mean scores of the sample in the form of bar graphs, frequency polygon, Ogive's representing the scores. 't' ratio was calculated to find out the no significant difference between the variables. 2 ways Anova was calculated to find out the interaction effect of gender and type of management.

Distribution on AASC

After compilation of the data in the form of scores of 120 students of secondary schools, it was considered obligatory to put the scores into distribution both component wise and totally in order to ascertain the tendency of scores obtained by the test towards normality through the application of parametric tests. All the parametric tests have certain basic assumptions, which are to be met in order to ascertain the result to be accurate. They are independence of observation, representation of scale of measurement, normality of the distribution and homogeneity of variance. The independence of observation denotes that the data obtained from different subject of the sample were independent which means that behavior of one participant did not influence the other. The variable was expressed in interval scale where the distance points of the scale were equal at all parts along the scale. Normality of the distribution refers to the study of scores with descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode and standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis and percentiles. Homogeneity of variance implied that the sample had nearly equal variances which are particularly important to determine when the samples are very small. As such the scores have been put into a total sample in table- 2 along with sex wise and management wise sub samples.

Table 2 Distributions of Scores on AASC

C.I	Gender		School type		Total
	Boys	Girls	Government	Private	
16-18	4	5	4	5	9
13-15	9	11	9	11	19
10-12	23	17	21	19	40
7-9	16	19	18	17	35
4-6	6	6	6	6	12
1-3	2	2	2	2	4

From the above table, it is quite clear that for the total sample the class interval 10-12 is considered as the modal class interval and for all the sub-category class interval 10-12 is considered as the modal class interval and the scores gradually narrows towards the upper and lower end. Such a distribution gives an impression of scores falling into a normal distribution.

Thus, the frequency and smooth frequency on Academic anxiety in students have been plotted into frequency polygon curve with the smooth frequency polygon superimposed on it.

Table 3 Calculations of Mean, Median, Mode, Standard Deviation, Quartile and Percentile for the Total Sample on AASC

Mean	Median	Mode	Standard Deviation	Q3	Q1	Q	P90	P10
10.19	10.17	10.13	3.69	12.18	3.8	4.19	12.18	4.29

In the normal distribution the mean, median, mode all coincide and there is slight variation between right and left of the figure but the distribution is positively Skewed that means the balance is shifted to the right. In the present investigation the value of skewness is +0.016 and therefore the distribution is positively skewed.

Moreover the kurtosis curve is more than the normal value of kurtosis which is 0.263. The calculated value is 0.53 which is more than the normal value of kurtosis which is 0.263. Since the calculated value is more from 0.263 and therefore the distribution is called Platykurtic, as the curve is flatter than the normal curve

Descriptive Measures on AASC

For studying the score distribution on AASC a frequency table is prepared from the data sheet and on the descriptive measures like Mean, Standard Deviation of the total sample as well as the sub-sample were calculated. The results are shown in table

Table 4 Table Mean, SD scores on AASC

Variables	Sub-Samples	No. of Students	Mean	SD
Gender	Boys	60	11.3	3.96
	Girls	60	10.19	3.63
School type	Government	60	11.09	3.56
	Private	60	10.31	3.72
Total		120	10.19	3.69

On perusal of the above table, it was observed that the total sub-sample Mean and SD was found to be 10.19 and 3.69 respectively. The Mean score of the boy students belonging to government school and private school was found to be higher than the total Mean score of other categories like girls showed same magnitude in mean scores when compared to the total mean score.

Sub-Sample Analysis on the scores on AASC

The sample was split into sub samples in relation to gender and school type. Thus following sub samples were built into the study namely:

- Boys v/s Girls
- Government school student's v/s private school students.

Gender Difference in the Scores on AASC

One of the objectives of the present investigation was to study the academic anxiety of students in relation to their gender. As such null hypothesis formulated in this respect was that "There will be no significant difference in academic anxiety of all the achievers in relation to their gender was put to test, through the test of no significances of the difference between means of the two groups as applicable to two independent samples. The result was presented in table.

Table 5 Difference in Gender on the scores of AASC

Gender	N	M	S.D	SED	't'	Remarks
Boys	60	11.3	3.96	0.693	1.601	Not Significant
Girls	60	10.19	3.63			

't' for df 118 at 0.5=1.98 and 0.01=2.63

The table value of 't' for the degree of freedom (118, 2) is higher than the calculated value of 't' (1.60). Hence, it could not be significant. Hence, the null hypothesis there does not exist any significant difference in the score of Academic anxiety test of the students in that relation to sex variation could not be rejected. The hypothesis was rather accepted coming to the conclusion the scores of academic anxiety of boys are equal to the scores of girls.

The study is in conformity with other researchers conducted by Latha. (2012), Bihari (2013) and Banga (2014). Hence, it may be concluded that the variable of sex had no role to play in the academic

anxiety scores and the results

Difference in Management on the scores of AASC

Another objective of the present investigation was to study the academic anxiety of students in relation to the type of management. As such null hypothesis formulated in this respect was that “There will be no significant difference in academic anxiety of all the achievers in relation to the type of management. Was put to test, through the test of no significances of the difference between means of the two groups as applicable to two independent samples. The result was presented in the table.

Table 6 Difference in Management on the scores of AASC

Management	N	M	S.D	SED	t	Remarks
Private	60	10.31	3.72	0.664	1.174	Not significant
Government	60	11.09	3.56			

t' for df 118 at 0.5=1.98 and 0.01=2.63

The table value of 't' for the degree of freedom (118, 2) is higher than the calculated value of 't' (1.60). Hence, it could not be significant. Hence the null hypothesis that there does not exist any significant difference in the score of Academic anxiety test of the students in that relation to management variation could not be rejected. The hypothesis was rather accepted coming to the conclusion the scores of academic anxiety of private schools are equal to the scores of Government schools.

The study is in conformity with other researchers conducted by Latha (2012), and Bihari (2013). Hence, it may be concluded that the variable of management had no role to play in the academic anxiety scores and the result obtained by the investigator can be considered appropriate in this investigation.

Interaction effect of Gender and type of Management on the scores of AASC

Another objective that the investigator studied was the interaction effect of gender and type of management on the scores of AASC .As such the null hypothesis formulated in this respect was that “There is no significant interaction effect of gender and type of management on academic anxiety of students” was put to test through two- ways Analysis of Variance among the variables gender and type of management

Table 7 Interactional effect of Gender and Type of Management on AASC

Sources of Variation	SS	df	MSV	F	Remarks
SSB	17.8	3	5.9	0.41	Not Significant
SSW	1677.4	116	14.5		
SST	1695.4				

'f' for df 116,3 at 0.5=3.07 and 0.01=4.78

The table value of 'f' for the degree of freedom (116, 3) is greater than the calculated value of 'f' (.41) hence it is not significant. Thus, the null hypothesis that there does not exist any significant effect in interaction effect of gender and type of management of academic anxiety of student is accepted. Thus, it can be concluded that there is no interaction effect of gender and type of management on academic anxiety level of students. The study is in conformity with the research conducted by Atiq and Siddiqui (2014). Hence, it may be concluded that the interaction effect of gender and type of management had no role to play in the academic anxiety scores and the result obtained by the investigator can be considered appropriate in this investigation.

Findings of the Study

The major findings of the study are as follows:

- The skewness and kurtosis scores were found to be 0.016 and 0.53 as against 0 and 0.263 respectively in case of a normal curve. Hence the distribution is positively skewed and Platykurtic.
- No Significant difference in the Academic anxiety in students was observed in relation to Gender i.e., Male and Female. In spite, of the Mean Score of Male (11.3) was higher than the Mean Score of Female (10.19).
- No Significant difference in the Academic anxiety in students was observed in relation to type of management. The Mean Score of government school was found to be 11.09 in case of less than private school
- No Significant difference in the interaction effect of gender and type of management on academic anxiety scores of students. The Mean Score within group was found to be (14.5) more than the mean score between the group.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Thus from the study it was observed. Inability to fare well academically has forced many children to resort to extreme steps. Thus it was essential to curb anxiety growing within them. Students usually suffered from anxiety because of their interference of negative thoughts and emotions during the period of examination, inadequate mastery of course material, inadequate academic self concept (Schunk, 1998), self motivation, self, efficiency, goal valuation, attitude towards school and teachers etc. (Reiss and Mc Coach, 2000), parental pressure, in capability of the student to prove themselves. It was found that students consistently perceive examination as a source of increase in anxiety.

The research entitled “An Interaction study of Academic Anxiety in relation to gender and school type among secondary school student” focused on the Academic anxiety in children.

The findings of the study were important for all parents, teachers, policy makers, administrators, so that they may take important steps for the management of anxiety within students at the secondary level. The following recommendations have been made on the findings of the present investigation:

- Academic anxiety influences the academic performance of the school students. The schools should start counselling centre for children and for parents as well.
- The counselling should be done by the expert counsellor and expert child psychologist; in order to encourage healthy lifestyle practices.
- The parents in particular and schools in general, need to encourage students to freely express themselves, impose lesser restrictions on them and appreciate their ideas.
- If the students anxiety is left untreated than it can lead or persist into adulthood,
- Academic anxiety is a severe problem of student studying in secondary students. Concerted efforts are needed to create an environment in schools free from anxiety by providing counselling to students.
- Teachers must create conducive environment in the classroom so that the students can be free from anxiety.
- Over expectations from the teachers and parents may lead them towards more academic anxiety. So in this regard, the parents and teachers must minimise their expectations for better academic performance of the child.

References

- Atleq, U.R and Siddiqui A.M (2014) Study of “ An Interaction study of Academic Anxiety in Relation to Socio-Economic Status, Gender and School type among Secondary School “ *International journal of Education Research and Technology* Vol:5(2)
- Banga lal Chaman (2014) study on “Academic Anxiety among high school students in relation to Gender and Type of family” *.Journal and Acomplete periodical dedicated to humanities and social Research* Vol:5(115)
- Banga Lal Chaman (2015) study on “A study of Academic Anxiety Among Private Senior Secondary School Students of Kangra District “. *International Journal of English language Literature and humanities* Vol: III
- Bhansali ,Reena and Trivedi Kunjan (2008) study of “Is Academic Anxiety Gender Specific: A Comparative Study“*J.Soc.Sci.*, 17 (1):1-3
- Deb Sibnath, Chatterjee Pooja, Wals Kerryann (2010) performed study on “Anxiety among high school students in India: Comparisons across gender, school type, social strata and perceptions of quality time with parents” *Australia Journal of educational and Developmental Psychology* Vol: 10(18)
- <http://www.nhti.edu/learningcenter/lctestanxiety>
- M. Latha (2012) study on “A Study of Self concept and Academic Anxiety among secondary school students of Mandya City “*International Multidisciplinary e-Journal* Vol: I(IX)
- Psychology definition.org/state-anxiety
- Psychology definition . O enen.wikipedia.org/wiki/stranger anxiety
- Socialanxietyinstitute.org/what-is-social-anxiety
- www.calmclinic.com/anxiety-treatments/somatic
- www.livestrong.com/...ferences-between-state-anxiety

The Attitude towards School among the Students of West Bengal

Sohel Rana Sarkar *
Dr. Abhijit Guha **

Abstract

How a student performs his role as a student depends to a great extent on his attitudes, values and beliefs. So, student's attitude towards school plays a vital and important role to make peaceful situation in school environment for the betterment of any society or nation which may promote complete citizen. The purpose of the study was to investigate the attitude of students towards their school which reveal the present scenario of student attitude towards their school. A total 185 students were randomly selected in the study. Different sets of test were administered to the sample of students to determine their attitude towards school.

Keywords: *Attitudes of Students, Elementary Level, Secondary level, Practice Teaching Schools, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira*

Introduction

Though 'live and let live' is the basic objective of social behaviour but due to fostering serious selfish attitude we have lost the spirit of 'live together'. The behavioural approach among the students in macro level has been influenced by this contemporary social environment. How we can constraint this radical change through critical investigation and analysis is - this is the first arena of this paper A school is considered as the miniature form of society. Both social goodness and evils are reflected in school. A nation's future is preparing in the classroom. Where education shall be directed toward the full development of the human personality and to the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall promote understanding, tolerance and friendship among all nations, racial or religious.

So, the positive attitude towards school of every single student is desirable.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives are given below:

- To study the difference in attitudes of students towards their school between the students of elementary level and secondary level.
- To study the present scenario of attitudes of students among the practice teaching schools under Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira (RKMSM).

* *Research Scholar, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belurmath.*

** *Associate Professor, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belurmath.*

.Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses are taken for the present enquiry:

Ho₁: There would be no significant difference in attitudes of students towards their school between the students of elementary level and secondary level.

Ho₂: There would be no significant difference in student attitudes towards schools among the different schools which are taken for this study.

Delimitation of the Study

The study has the following delimitations:

- i. The study is delimited to those students who are studying at the elementary level and secondary level of the practice teaching schools under Ramakrishna Mission.
- ii. The study is delimited to those students who are studying at the elementary level and secondary level of the practice teaching schools under Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira.
- iii. The study is delimited to only five practice teaching schools under RKMSM.

Methodology of the Study

In this investigation, the investigator was considered following two types of variables.

A) Major Variables

- I. Student's Attitude towards School.

B) Categorical Variables

- I. Elementary Level and Secondary Level student.
- II. Students belonging to different practice teaching schools under RKMSM.

Sample

The 185 secondary level students were selected randomly from the five (5) practice teaching schools under RKMSM. of Hooghly or Howrah district.

Table 1: Sample frame of the student Level Wise

Students' Level	No. of Students	TOTAL
Elementary level students	103	185
Secondary level students	82	

Table 2: Sample frame of the students School Wise

No. of School	School 1	School 2	School 3	School 4	School 5	Total Sample
No. of Students	35	41	43	25	41	185

(Where the schools are: Belur High School=1, Bhadrakali High School=2, Uttarpara Amarendranath School=3, Makhla High School=4, Kotrong Bhupendra Smriti Vidyalaya=5)

Tool used for the Study

The researcher used one standardized scales as research tools. The scale was “Students' Attitude Towards School Scale (SATSS)” developed and standardized by Paul and Guha (2014).

Validity and Reliability of the Tool

Content validity was done by the expert rating of items by two experts. The inter-rating agreement model was used (Gregory, 2005) to see reliability of the ratters. The coefficient of content validity of 'SATSS' was 0.84 and reliability of the scale was computed by using Cronbach's Alpha and was found 0.79 for SATSS.

Procedure of Data Collection

The researcher personally visited the five (5) practice teaching schools under RKMSM for the collection of data in one phase. At first, students were given a short instruction regarding filling in of their response sheet. They asked to response according to their own belief and thought without any consultation with another student and to submit the above responded sheets.

Analysis and Interpretation

The result of the study are presented as below:

Group statistics of SATSS under first categorical variable

Categorical Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Elementary level	103	112.4078	14.464	1.425
Secondary level	82	112	16.066	1.774

Objective wise analysis of data: To fulfil the 2 objectives, 2 null hypotheses are formulated and tested here. Interpretations of the results are also given below.

Objective No. 1

- To study the difference in attitudes of students towards their school between the students of elementary level and secondary level.

To fulfil this objective, one null hypothesis is formulated and tested which is as follows:

Ho₁: There would be no significant difference in attitudes of students towards their school between the students of elementary level and secondary level.

Testing of Ho₁

To test the Ho₁, descriptive and inferential statistics are computed and the above results are given below:

Groups: Students of elementary level and secondary level.

Group statistics and t test for equality of mean differences in attitudes of students towards their school between the students of elementary level and secondary level							
Group statistics					t- Test for equality of means		
First Categorical Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig.(2 tailed)
Elementary level	103	112.4078	14.464	1.425	1.973**	183	0.856
Secondary level	82	112	16.066	1.774			

Interpretation

From the analyses it is seen that in case of peace attitudes of students towards their school between the students of elementary level and secondary level the calculated t (df=183) value is 1.973 and p value is 0.856 ($p > 0.05$). Hence, t is not significant at 0.05 level. So, Ho₁ is not rejected and it can be safely said that elementary level student are not significantly different from the secondary level students in respect to their attitudes towards peace in school.

Objective No. 2

- To study the present scenario of peace attitudes of student among the practice teaching schools under RKMSM.

To fulfil this objective, one null hypothesis is formulated and tested which is as follows:

Ho₁: There would be no significant difference in peace attitudes of students among the different schools which are taken for this study.

Testing of Ho₂

To test the **Ho₂** descriptive and inferential statistics are computed and the above results are given below:

Schools: (**Belur High School=1, Bhadrakali High School=2, Uttarpara Amarendranath School=3, Makhla High School=4, Kotrong Bhupendra Smriti Vidyalaya=5)

Group statistics					F- Test for equality of means		
Second Categorical Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	F	df	Sig. (2tailed)
School 1	35	108.428	16.608	2.807	2.421**	180	0.022
School 2	41	117.512	16.235	2.535			
School 3	43	114.953	15.623	2.382			
School 4	25	109.56	10.124	2.024			
School 5	41	108.951	13.262	2.071			

Interpretation

To identify the significant difference, if any, in peace attitudes of student among the different practice teaching schools under RKMSM by ANNOVA, 5 Schools were conveniently selected from practice

teaching schools under RKMSM here total sample acts as a sample frame. Descriptive statics of each group of students have been shown in table 5.

Findings

From the analyses in Table 5 it is seen that in case of peace attitudes of student among different schools which are taken for this study the calculated F (180) value is 2.421 and p value is 0.022 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, F is significant at 0.05 level. So, the hypothesis is rejected and it can be conclude that there is a significant difference in peace attitudes of student among the different practice teaching schools under RKMSM and because of having significance among the schools, it is require for further 't' test between the Schools.

Combination of 10 Schools for further 't' test:

10 Groups are: (Where the Schools are: Belur High School=1, Bhadrakali High School=2, Uttarpara Amarendranath School=3, Makhla High School=4, Kotrong Bhupendra Smriti Vidyalaya=5)

- a) (school 1 & 2); b) (school 1 & 3); c) (school 1 & 4); d) (school 1 & 5);
 e) (school 2 & 3); f) (school 2 & 4); g) (school 2 & 5); h) (school 3 & 4);
 l) (school 3 & 5); j) (school 5 & 4).

In further 't' test, from the analyses it is seen that among 10 in school combination, 7 combination of schools i.e. b. (school 1 & 3), c. (school 1 & 4), d. (school 1 & 5), e. (school 2 & 3), h. (school 3 & 4), i. (school 3 & 5) and j. (school 5 & 4) have the greater p value ($p > 0.05$). Hence, 't' is not significant at 0.05 level. So, it can be concluded that there are no significant difference in attitudes of students among the taken schools combination and another 3 combination of schools i.e. a. (school 1 & 2), f. (school 2 & 4), g. (school 2 & 5), have significant difference which are given below:

Group a: School 1 and School 2 (1=Belur High School, 2=Bhadrakali High School)

Group statistics and 't' test for equality of mean differences in peace attitudes of student between 2 practice teaching schools under RKMSM.					t- Test for equality of means		
Group statistics					t	df	Sig. (2tailed)
Categorical Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean			
School 1	35	108.428	16.608	2.807	1.992*	74	0.018
School 2	41	117.512	16.235	2.535			

Interpretation

From the analyses in Table 6. it is seen that in case of attitudes of students towards their school between Belur High School and Bhadrakali High the calculated 't' (74) value is 1.992 and p value is 0.018 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, t is significant at 0.05 level. So, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in peace attitudes of student between Belur High and Bhadrakali High School.

Group f: School 2 and School 4. (2=Bhadrakali High School & 4=Makhla High School).

Group statistics and 't' test for equality of mean differences in peace attitudes of student between 2 practice teaching schools under RKMSM.							
Group statistics					t- Test for equality of means		
Categorical Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig.(2 tailed)
School 2	41	103.682	12.964	2.024	1.997**	64	0.031
School 4	25	109.56	10.124	2.024			

Interpretation:

From the analyses in Table 7 it is seen that in case of attitudes of students towards their school between Bhadrakali High School and Makhla High School the calculated t (64) value is 1.997 and p value is 0.031 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, t is significant at 0.05 level. So, it can be clearly said that there is a significant difference in peace attitudes of student between Bhadrakali High School and Makhla High School.

Group g: School 2 and School 5 (2=Bhadrakali High School and 5=KotrongBhupendra Smriti Vidyalaya).

Group statistics and 't' test for equality of mean differences in peace attitudes of student between 2 practice teaching schools under RKMSM.							
Group statistics					t- Test for equality of means		
Categorical Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig.(2 tailed)
School 2	41	103.682	12.964	2.024	1.990**	80	0.010
School 5	41	101.878	11.097	1.733			

Interpretation:

From the analyses in Table 8 it is seen that in case of attitudes of students towards their school between Bhadrakali High School and Kotrong Bhupendra Smriti Vidyalaya the calculated t (64) value is 1.990 and p value is 0.010 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, t is highly significant at 0.05 level. So, it can be clearly said that there is a significant difference in peace attitudes of student between Bhadrakali High School and Kotrong Bhupendra Smriti Vidyalaya.

The Major Findings

To compare the attitudes of students towards their school under different variables, Students' Attitude Towards School Scale (SATSS) – appendix (1) was applied. After scoring, the data were analysed through MS excel 2010 the findings are as follows:

- I) The mean score of SATSS among 185 students in 5 schools was found 112.227 which are above the average (score ranged from 32 to 160). Thus from this statistics it may assume that school students under RKMSM practice teaching school of west Bengal possess a moderate positive peace attitude towards school.
- ii) Elementary level student are not significantly different from secondary level student in respect to their peace attitude towards School. The mean score of elementary level student (112.4078) of SATSS was slightly higher than secondary level student mean score (112). It means that elementary level student insignificantly possesses a positive peace attitude Towards School than the secondary level student in learning process in school.
- iii) Elementary level student are not significantly different from the secondary level students in respect to their attitudes towards peace in school.

The findings related to the present scenario of peace attitudes of student among the practice teaching schools under RKMSM.

In the light of the objectives after completion of data analysis and interpretation, several points have come out and the major findings are as follows:

- i) The mean score of SATSS among 185 students in 5 schools was found 112.227 which is above the average (score ranged from 32 to 160). Thus from this statistics it may assume that school students under RKMSM practice teaching school of west Bengal possess a moderate positive peace attitude towards school.
- ii) The mean score of **peace attitudes of student** in different schools are School 1 (108.428),

School 2 (117.512), School 3 (114.953), School 4 (109.56) & School 5 (108.951). through the analysis it is clear that School 2 (117.512) of SATSS was slightly higher than rest 4 school's mean score School 1 (108.428), School 3 (114.953), School 4 (109.56) and School 5 (108.951).

- iii) There will be a significant difference in peace attitudes of student among the different practice teaching schools under RKMSM. The groups which have significant these are as follows:

Group a): School 1 and School 2

- i) The mean score of school 1 (108.428) of SATSS was less than school 2 mean score (117.512). It means that school 2 student is insignificantly possess a positive peace attitude Towards School than the school 1 student.
- ii) There will be a significant difference in peace attitudes of student between school 1 and school 2.

(where, *1= Belur High School and 2=Bhadrakali High School.)

Group f): School 2 and School 4

- i) The mean score of school 2 (103.682) of SATSS was less than school 4 mean score (109.56). It means that school 4 student is insignificantly possess a positive peace attitude Towards School than the school 2 student.
- ii) There will be a significant difference in peace attitudes of student between school 2 and school 4.

(where, *2=Bhadrakali High School & 4=Makhla High School).

Group g): School 2 and School 5

- i) The mean score of school 2 (103.682) of SATSS was higher than school 5 mean score (101.878). It means that school 2 student is insignificantly possess a positive peace attitude Towards School than the school 5 student.
- ii) There will be a significant difference in peace attitudes of student between school 2 and school 5.

(where *2=Bhadrakali High School and 5=Kotrong Bhupendra Smriti Vidyalaya).

Discussion

To compare the attitudes of students towards their school elementary level student are not significantly different from secondary level student in respect to their peace attitude towards School. The mean score of elementary level student of SATSS was slightly higher than secondary level student mean score. It means that elementary level student is insignificantly possess a positive peace attitude Towards School than the secondary level student in learning process in school.

The mean score of peace attitude towards school is above the average. Thus from this statistics it may be assumed that school students under RKMSM practice teaching school of West Bengal possess a moderate positive peace attitude towards school. There will be a significant difference in peace attitudes of student among the different practice teaching schools under RKMSM.

Conclusion

The attitude of the student must be positive because the learning to make a living is not the sole reason for getting education; there is another, equally important by product: learning to make a life, a life that is beneficial, useful and peaceful. After all, humans are social animals; their success in life is largely a matter of successful social relations. Quite evidently, student age is the crucially important period which enriches one's personal life, nurtures social adjustments, fosters friendship and understanding and affects one's whole life pattern. Seen from this perspective, one could very well understand the critical necessity of teaching students, youth and young leaders the art of living together, in mutual respect, justice, love and peace.

References:

- Bailliet, C., & Larsen, K. M. (2015). *Promoting peace through international law* (1st ed.). Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Page, J. S. (2008). *Peace education: Exploring ethical and philosophical foundations*. Charlotte, NC: Information Age Publication.
- Webel, C., & Galtung, J. (2007). *Handbook of peace and conflict studies*. London: Routledge.
- Nhật, H., & Kotler, A. (1987). *Being peace*. Berkeley, Calif.: Parallax Press.
- Navarro-Castro, L., & Nario-Galace, J. (2008). *Peace Education*. Filipinas: Center For Peace Education.
- Fedorenko, V. (2012). *The role of civil society in peacebuilding, conflict resolution, and democratization*. Washington, DC: Rethink Institute.

- Upadhyay, P. (2010). *Education for peace: Utopia or reality*. Delhi: Kalpaz Publications.
- Borkar, U. A. (2014). Transacting Peace Education in School Using PETS—A Study. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 4(1), 30-34.
- Toohy, D. E. (2014). Introduction: The Effect of Inclusion and Exclusion on Positive Peace. *International Journal of Peace Studies*, 18(2), 1-4.
- Nair, G. (2010). Peace education and conflict resolution in school. *Health Administrator*, XVII(1), 38-42.
- Gregor, L. M. (2006). Beyond the time and space of peace talks: re-appropriating the peace process in srilanka. *International Journal of Peace Studies*, 11(1), 39-57.
- Pruitt, L. (2011). Creating a musical dialogue for peace. *International Journal of Peace Studies*, 16(1), 81-101.
- Reychler, L. (2006). Challenges of peace research. *International Journal of Peace Studies*, 11(1), 1-16.
- Tint, B. S., & Prasad, G. K. (2007). Peace Education in India: Academics, Politics, and Peace. *The Canadian Journal of Peace and Conflict Studies*, 39(1), 23-37.
- Yeh, T. D. (2006). The way to peace: a Buddhist perspective. *International Journal of Peace Studies*, 11(1), 91-112.

Anxiety in Women Teachers and its Impact on Adjustment of their Own Children

Pratistha Kumari *

Abstract

Teachers' performance is the extent of teacher's mastery over the subject matter and desirable personal qualities conducive to the profession such as, confidence, morality, and regularity, emotional intelligence balance of mind communication skills and task orientation and evaluation. But social interaction jobs ' demands and pressures vary from person to person. In the context of equality of men and women, and more women now given job opportunities in the name of women empowerment, our country with huge diversity in socio economic and cultural scenario faces challenges of stability and peaceful co- existence. As all over the world, there is a general trend of recruiting women teachers in schools, and all the married women teachers are performing dual responsibilities of managing home as well as accepting job for earning a living, the role of women in bringing up the development in children is at stake. Such women are under serious problems of stress and hence fail to give adequate attention towards the study of their children. In this study , it is revealed that women teachers had developed anxiety due to certain socio- demographic variables and there was significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and level of adjustment of their own children.

Key words: Anxiety, Women Empowerment, Peaceful Co-existence, Socio-Demographic Variables

Introduction

Anxiety

Anxiety is just a part of life. It helps us cope with the stresses we may encounter. However, following the emergence and influence of the modern life style, the traditional society has lost its monopoly. Children are separated from their parents for a longer period because of the dual earning system and workaholic mania of the parents. Children spend more time outside in schools and peer groups and therefore are unable to get parental guidance. The school, on the other hand which should play this role tends to lay its emphasis on academic pursuits and success. The teachers who spend a lot of time with the youngsters are loaded with full normal teaching workload and hence do not offer adequate time to the guidance counseling service.

A guidance vacuum has therefore created in this area. There is therefore the need for progressive development of relationship between a person's level of arousal and ability to function effectively.

**Pratistha Kumari, Research Scholar, Utkal University*

However, when a person is too anxious, the anxiety may interfere with performance, because the individual's concentration tends to focus too much on his/ her anxiety build up process. The reality painted above, has been the driving force behind the different people's efforts to devise methods of dealing with challenges paused by anxiety related problems in different generations.

One of the important motivators in the educational milieu is anxiety. It describes individual's level of emotionality. Individuals sometimes distinguish among their friends, those who are tensed and worried and those who are cool. Since anxiety is an invert emotional state of the organism they can't be directly observed, investigations of anxiety rely heavily upon the individual's report of his own emotional state under various stress conditions. Therefore anxiety and arousal are related. Educational

**Pratistha Kumari, Research Scholar, Utkal University*

psychologists have studied the students' experiences under the stressful conditions of taking a test. This refers to the emotional state or anxiety of students.

Anxiety is a threat to the “core or essence” of personality. It is a reaction to threat to what the individual holds essential to his existence as personality. Individual develops some pattern as the basis of one's safety. Anything which is likely to jeopardize the individual's specific protective pursuits may provoke anxiety, (Horney, 1959).

Adjustment constitutes as important part of this Science. Psychology attempts to understand, to control and to explain the dynamics of complex interpersonal human behaviour. It also enables us to improve our understanding of the ways in which the people meet the changes of daily life and fulfill the physical, psychological or social needs. The process of needs arousal continues throughout the life of human beings. This process of needs arousal and their satisfaction is in a broad sense, adjustment. In psychology adjustment plays as important role in shaping one's self-concept. The investigations conducted by Rother (1990), Mukhopadhyaya (1991), Alexander and Rajendran (1992), Abu-Ein (1995), Roja Rani (1995), Sarsani (2007), Das (2008), Sharma (2010) throw light to this. The concept therefore needs elaboration

Adjustment

The concept of adjustment is as old as human race on earth. The systematic emergence of the concept starts from Darwin's theory of “Survival of the Fittest” Essentially adjustment refers to the ability of

an individual to satisfy the demands of his surrounding as well as his own needs. The dictionary meaning of the word “adjustment” is to fit, make suitable, adapt. Arrange, modify, harmonize or make correspondent. Thus when we make adjustment between two things, we adapt or modify one or both of them to correspond to each other. At the psychological level, adjustment means the individuals struggle to survive in his/her surroundings. The emphasis is on the functional or learned changes the individual must make to achieve a harmonious relationship with the environment while satisfying our urge; the other unsatisfied impulses create tension. In such a case mental, physical and balance is missed and the individual suffers from frustration. By Adjustment man makes himself free from mental tension and fulfils his requirements. At the time of birth the child is fully dependent on others. His requirements are fulfilled by the members of his family and society. His environment seems to him mysterious as a spider nest. All the persons and objects around him seem to be alike. But gradually when he becomes older he applies his power to protection, sensation and conception and gains better knowledge about surroundings.

In adjustment, the two crucial factors are the individual and the environment. In the individual the considerations are the heredity and biological factors the psychological factors and the quality of socialization given to him or her where environment includes all the social factors. “While considering adjustment as a process we are interested in the way the individuals modifies or inhibits his internal impulses or alters the environmental demands to eliminate the conflicts,” (Lazarus, 1961).

Adjustment is a condition or state in which the individual's behaviour conforms to the demands of the culture or society to which he belongs and he feels that his own needs have been or will be fulfilled. It involves the gratification of a person's needs as governed by the demands of various environmental situations. This is not however, a one way process: an individual maintains the balance between himself and his surroundings either by modifying his own behaviour or by modifying the environment. In this context Arkoff (1968) states “Adjustment is the interaction between a person and his environment. How one adjusts in a particular situation depends upon one's personal characteristics as also the circumstances of the situation. In other words, both personal and environmental factors work side by side in adjustment. An individual is adjusted if he is adjusted to himself and to his environment”.

Adjustment has been interpreted in two ways i.e. adjustment as achievement and adjustment as a

process. Adjustment as achievement implies the effectiveness (good, satisfactory or bad) with which an individual can function in changed circumstances. It is accomplished either badly or well. It makes possible the comparison of individuals in terms of their adjustive adequacy in society. Adjustment as a process describes and explains the ways and means of an individual's adaptation to his self and his environment without reference to the quality of such adjustment or its outcome in terms of success or failure. It only shows how individuals or a group or groups of people cope under changing circumstances and what factors influence this adjustment. Good adjustment is absolutely essential for happy and effective adulthood. Such good adjustment ideally is developed from infancy onwards. However, if good adjustment is not possible in childhood, adolescence is the best time for achieving it, further it is not correct to say that this is the final opportunity. Adjustment is a continuous process in human life.

The term adjustment mostly refers to the degree of capacity by which an individual tries to cope-up with the needs of inner tensions, conflicts, frustration and simultaneously is able to bring coordination between his inner demands and those by the outer world. Adjustment in school is recognized as a multi-faceted process that demand children's internal resources and prior learning, family support mechanisms, and qualities of the school environment to generate the behaviors, dispositions, and skills that are used to describe the “well adjusted child.”(Harrison,2004).

The process of adjustment starts from the birth of the child and continues throughout life. The nature of the adjustment of an individual is governed by biological factors as well as the social experiences which he receives in his environment. Adjustment as process is dynamic complex and continuing process through which individuals respond to their ever changing needs and desires with a variety of behaviors in order to adjust adequately in their social environment. It is a proven fact that adolescence is a time when so many new adjustments are being made, when social relations are of great importance. When there is much idealism and optimism about the future, it is the opportune time for accomplishing major changes in outlook in life, attitude towards self, emotional control and the like.

Adjustment of a school child is highly essential. The role of the school in accelerating the process of adjustment is of paramount importance. Good adjustment accelerates activity and leads to better outcomes. The amount of growth and development of the children depends on the degree of their adjustment. Since adjustment depends on situations and situations can be modified in a desirable direction, the adjustment level of children can be raised for better results. This is possible only when

we know the current adjustment levels of the children.

Role of Women in Children's Development

When one considers the all- round development of children, responsibility is thrust upon the women, who look for the total well being of their children. In the modern contest, heavy burden on the children due work load given by the schools as homework leaves the children undone, for which they find no time to play in open grounds or to rejoice after coming back from schools. In case of the working women, the children are left at homes uncared for. In the absence of both the working parents, the children spend their time fearlessly by witnessing TV serials,, working with internets, playing with mobiles and discovering from internet all impermissible events to discover what is in that ,due to the nature of adolescent characteristics. In order to have holistic development of the child, the social, emotional needs of the child must be taken care of. Children need love, care affection and a feeling of security as well as freedom of will. Healthy emotional well being comes out from social, emotional relationships and the willingness to share with others. This begins at home and grows gradually. The home is to cater to the needs of the adolescents. But in the present context of social ostracism practiced in the society, the religious fanaticism, corruption in public life, regionalism, rivalry and superstitious beliefs have become strong impediments to the social, moral, emotional and intellectual development of children. The home which takes keenly the care of children, enables them to grow into socially responsible and competent citizen with proper adjustment at home, school, society and the nation. But where the home is left by both the working parents and taken care of maids, parents don't have time to spend with their children; in that case, the personality development of children is subjected to risk factors. More so, if the mother is working, the children are devoid of mother care and love. Mother's place is irreplaceable at home. Absence of mother at home is a curse in the lives of the children. In order to guard these children from the ill effects of the mass media, bad company and many more society's anti- social activities, the mother has to discharge responsibilities as a loving and caring mother ,so that in course of time, they would properly adjust to the varying circumstances that may confront them.

As more and more women are seeking employment outside the home, there is dearth of child care and home making. Maximum women opting for the teaching profession is now confronted with the job at working place, management of home, and child's all- round development. In the Indian context, this dual role in case of women is making them worried and they are always in anxiety as to do how and

when. In this juncture, naturally they are frustrated and anxiety prone due to stress and burn out. Therefore, the following question arises, “what are the effects of working mothers' on their family environment and education of children? Are the women teachers, who are mothers capable of tackling the situation comfortably or are isolated from the main stream because of tensions and anxieties due to their role performance?” But they are undone, because most of them find difficulty in home management financially. Because of poverty they prefer to work even at a very less amount of salary. This has been aggravated in India, specifically due to the fact that very less amount of GDP spent on education is dismally less to pay to the teachers as per rules for which Govt decides a very low pay scale, that to on adhoc or contractual basis. Taking clue from that there is mushroom growth of private schools which are extracting the human resource at a miserable condition. In case of English medium schools, this is very acute. Such a state of affair in case of working women teachers has given rise to disruptive effects on marriages and family life. This is a great problem and cause for development of anxieties in working women teachers doing the dual role of rearing children at home and serving in schools for maintenance. Even though the added income does not necessarily end the financial crisis of the family, the working mother cannot give up the job. It is bound to cause a lot of harm at the cost of child care. The energy of women are drained for the extra burden on them. Even if these tasks are shared by the partners, yet everyone is so tired by the end of the day's work that minor disturbances quickly flare into major disruptions and this might be the cause for conflicts at home and broken homes. Hence women are subjected to be seriously anxiety prone. Withdrawal of parental indulgence set off adjustment problems in children from the very young age. Family being the most important of all the environmental influences in the shaping of the personality of the child becomes obligatory on the part of the people to reduce anxiety and take care of the children in the early years of their lives. Hence a mother's anxiety reduction and maintaining mental peace is evident. If anxiety would be developed, she can never be successful neither doing justice in schools, nor doing mother's role for enabling her own children to be adjustable along with a bright career in the field of academics.

Rationale of the Study

The quality of education depends on the teachers. They have an important influence on students' academic achievement. An effective teacher as an embodiment of knowledge and personification of

reality influences on the child in respect of his behavior along with the transactional process. In the entire teaching – learning process, the teacher is a powerful agent who can inculcate good habits and attitudes, democratic ideas of nation hood in the children. High achievement of the students, molding children into better citizens and exposing them in the growing area of competition can become possible only when teachers are efficient, energetic, dedicated and effective. **d strain.**

Normally, parents are a child's first teachers. Parents' actions reinforce some kind of behavior and discourage others, thus helping to determine habits, goals and values . The techniques the child learns in dealing with parents carry over into contacts with other people. Boys and girls are rewarded differently by different families. Hence in the family, pressure is always there as it produces some of the personality and adjustment differences. Parents, who are themselves adjusted, give the children a feeling of self worth and the self confidence with their praise and love. This helps in development of desirable attitude in children and adjustment mechanisms. But there is evidence that parents reject their children of their own emotional problems. This gives scope to the children in developing maladjustment and un- sociable characteristics.

Women are the important human resource of the nation. A nation can only develop, only when its women are given enough opportunities to contribute to national development. The women make vital contributions by playing dynamic roles in the upliftment of the family and as an earning unit. Research in women related issues have clearly revealed that educated urban working women are under social and economic oppression and discriminations at homes, in schools, working places. Women in general are in very low and pathetic condition, which are forcing them to develop serious anxieties to cope up with the situation. This leads them to severe problematic situations. As a result, the very purpose of women empowerment, increase in national productivity and bringing equal status between men and women has become a threat to the nation. The socio- economic and demographic background of women working in schools affect the value orientation of women teachers and all these factors influence human anxiety. Children need love and affection, a feeling of security, freedom. Therefore, the main aim of education is to shape the character of the children and make them persons of high morality. Values are to be inculcated in them by providing activities and experience. Values related to both cognitive and affective domains are to be integrated into the personality for their character formation. Therefore, married women teachers are required to discharge the duties at home and in schools.. But the present status of women teachers in schools is so

pathetic that it leads to anxiety in them in their personal lives. Therefore a need was felt by the investigator to study the anxiety in mother women teachers and its effect on their own children's adjustment. The significance of the study was considered in the light of non-availability of prior research in this area, after maximum women were given chance to serve as teachers in different schools. The study was also unique in the state of Odisha. Broken homes, divorce cases, dowry systems which are the impediments to social development, were due to the question of non-combating the anxiety level of mothers. Therefore the significance of the study owes a great relevance in the present socio cultural set up

Statement of the Problem

“Anxiety in women teachers and its impact on Adjustment of their own children”

Objectives

1. To study the anxiety level of women teachers in relation to some of the socio-demographic variables.
2. To study the effect of anxiety level of women teachers on the level of adjustment of their own children.
3. To study the level of adjustment of the children of working women teachers.

Formulation of Hypotheses

All the hypotheses have been formulated in null form for verification and interpretation of results.

H₀: There is no significant association between the anxiety levels of women teachers in relation to some of the socio- demographic variables.

- 1.1 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and their age levels.
- 1.2 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and their educational qualifications.
- 1.3 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and their experience in teaching.
- 1.4 There is no significant association between anxiety level of women teachers and their satisfaction in their jobs of teaching.

1.5 There is no significant association between anxiety level of women teachers and the financial status of their family.

1.6 There is no significant association between anxiety level of women teachers and the disturbances in their family.

1.7 There is no significant association between anxiety level of women teachers and the disturbances in their family.

1.8 There is no significant association between the anxiety levels of women teachers in relation to the marital status variation.

Ho₂: There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the level of adjustment of their children.

2.1 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the social adjustment of their children.

2.2 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the emotional adjustment of their children.

2.3 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the educational adjustment of their children.

2.4 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the social adjustment of boys.

2.5 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the emotional adjustment of boys

2.6 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the educational adjustment of boys.

2.7 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the social adjustment of girls

2.8 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the emotional adjustment of girls

2.9 There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the educational adjustment of girls

H₀: There are no significant sex differences in the levels of adjustment of the boy and girl children of the working women teachers' component wise.

- 3.1 There is no significant sex difference in boy and girl children of working women teachers in the levels of social adjustment
- 3.2 There is no significant sex difference boy and girl children of working women teachers in the levels of emotional adjustment
- 3.3 There is no significant sex difference in boy and girl children of working women teachers in the levels of educational adjustment.

Operational Definitions

'Anxiety' here refers to the measure of manifest anxiety as per Anxiety scale of Sinha (1998). It takes into account age related situations that affect on individual's anxiety and is glared more towards mid life issues such as fear of ageing, dying. Components include worry, over sensitivity, physiological anxieties, social concerns stress, low self control, emotionality and suspiciousness.

“Women teachers” refer to married teachers working in secondary schools.

'Adjustment' here is conceived as per the AISS of Sinha and Singh (2013) in social, emotional and educational area.

Significance of the Study

The fact is that anxiety, temperament, adjustment and academic achievement are interlinked to a great extent. Anxiety being a negative factor affects the academic achievement of a student. In such a situation, temperament and adjustment act as motivating factors to contribute to the success of students' performance. Hence, the investigator is able to find out the number of related literature on temperament, adjustment and academic achievement.

The investigator would like to add the following critical comments starting with the variable anxiety. After the critical evaluation of the studies related to anxiety, the investigator has made the following conclusions.

The present study is unique for several reasons. It is understood that no study has been undertaken so far that had anxiety of women teachers' and children's adjustment. Hence it is understood that the present study is the first in its kind in this aspect. Several studies have been conducted on different

groups having anxiety as its focus. But it is understood that no study has so far been conducted on secondary school children, therefore the study stands unique.

No Indian investigators have focused exclusively on the anxiety level, job stress of women teachers and its impact on the children's schooling. Therefore the study remains unique.

The Method of Study

The purpose of the study was to find out the relationship between the variables of anxiety of women and its impact on their school going children on their academic achievement. So it is a descriptive research type which describes and interprets, "what is". It is concerned with relations that exists, opinions that are held,, processes that is going on, effect that are evident or trends that are developing. Therefore in this study an ex- post- facto research design was adopted which investigated the relationships among variables when already manifestations have occurred.

The sample for the study consisted of 106 married women teachers and 106 secondary school students who are their own children of which 48 were boys and 58 were girls reading in classes VIII to IX in CBSE pattern Secondary Schools of Bhubaneswar Municipal Corporation.

Tools used

The following tools were used to collect the data;

1. Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety Scale
2. A Personal Data Blank of the women teachers was developed by the investigator to keep record of women teachers as per the requirement to spell out the mediator variables.
3. Adjustment Inventory for School Students (AISS)2013

The descriptions of different areas of the Inventory were also spelt out.

Emotional Adjustment refers to the emotional stability. High scores in this area indicated unstable emotion; where as low scores predicted the children to be emotionally stable.

Social Adjustment refers to submissive and aggressive behavior. Individuals scoring high are submissive and low scores indicate aggressive behavior.

Educational Adjustment refers to Individuals scoring high are poorly adjusted with their curricular and co- curricular programme, where as individuals scoring low are found interested in school programme.

Techniques of Analysis

For interpretation of scores of all the variables both descriptive and inferential statistics were used. Descriptive statistics were made use of to determine the respondents standing in the three situations where as inferential statistics were used as techniques of analysis for subsamples to find out intra differences due to the attribute variables. The Chi Square of Independence was adopted to find out the association between the independent and dependent variables. The 't' ratio was also adopted wherever it was found to be necessary.

Results

Association between levels of anxiety of working women teachers in relation to socio demographic variables.

Association between anxiety level of women teachers and their age

The association between anxiety level of women teachers and their age was considered in order to assess whether any significant association existed between anxiety level of women teachers and their age. The calculated chi-square was found to be 50.46, which was much greater than the table value 13.277 at 0.01 level of significance for df 4. It was therefore concluded that anxiety in women teachers differed as a function of age. Therefore, the null hypotheses $H_{0,1}$ that there is no significant association between anxiety level of women teachers and their age level was rejected. This meant that there was a very big gap between the expected and observed frequencies in the anxiety levels of women teachers due to their age levels.

Association between anxiety levels of women teachers and their educational qualifications.

In order to study whether the anxiety levels of women teachers are influenced by their educational qualification, a chi-square test was adopted. It was observed that the calculated chi-square value was found to be 22.03 which is much more than the table value of 13.277 at 0.01 level of significance for 4 degrees of freedom. It was therefore concluded that, the null hypothesis $H_{0,2}$ that there was no significant association between anxiety level of women teachers and their educational qualification was rejected.

Association between anxiety levels of women teachers and their experience in teaching.

In order to study whether anxiety level in women teachers as a function of their experience in teaching, the null hypothesis $H_{0,3}$ was formulated that there is no significant difference between

women teachers' anxiety levels and their teaching experience. In order to verify this hypothesis, the chi-square test of independence was calculated by considering the women teachers' high, average and low level of anxiety in correspondence with their teaching experience. It was observed from the table, that the calculated chi-square value was found to be 34.74 which was significant at 0.01 level of significance as the table value for the same was 13.277 at 4 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis $H_{0_{1,3}}$ that there is no significant association between the anxiety levels of women teachers and their experiences in teaching was rejected. It revealed that the anxiety level of women teachers was significantly associated with their teaching experience.

Association between anxiety levels of women teachers and their job satisfaction in teaching profession.

Job satisfaction also claims as one of the factors for development of anxiety. Padmini (2000) in a study found out no association with development of anxiety in women and their job satisfaction. Development of anxiety is due to job satisfaction was reported in the studies of Gupta(1987), Laskar(2008), Nurdan(2010). So in the present study the investigator attempted to investigate whether there is any significant association between anxiety level of women teachers and their job satisfaction. For this the chi-square test of independence was calculated and found to be 8.01 is much less than the table value of 9.488 to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence. Hence the null hypothesis formulated in that context that there is no significant association between the anxiety levels of women teachers and their job satisfaction was accepted. It was therefore concluded that there is no significant association between anxiety levels of women teachers and their job satisfaction.

Association between anxiety level of women teachers and the financial status of their families.

The financial status of the women teachers were assessed by administering the Personal Data Blank. Their opinions regarding the status of the family financially were collected under three modes like, Acute, Average and Not at all. This was done with a view to ascertaining the smooth maintenance of their house hold problems. Income of the family is a great influencing factor for maintaining smooth livelihood. Whether financial status plays a vital role in generating anxiety in women teachers, it was thought to include this in the present investigation. It was observed that the calculated Chi-square value being 14.51 is much greater than the table value of 13.277 at 0.01 level of significance for 4 degrees of freedom. Hence it is significant. Therefore, it was concluded that, there is significant

association between the anxiety level of women teachers and their financial status. The divergence between the expected and the obtained frequencies revealed that, the anxiety levels of women teachers are significantly associated with the financial status of their families.

Association between anxiety level of women teachers and the Disturbances in their families.

Family disturbance also is a major cause for generating anxiety in the people. The women teachers at present are facing acute problems in family due to many factors like the burden of family size, number of family members, number of dependents upon only one or two earning members, present day style of living, care for elderly persons, relationship in siblings etc. The other reasons may be non compatibility between married partners and burden in family owing to unmarried daughters even if they are self sufficient. Taking this clue in mind, the investigator intended to examine if family disturbance is a cause for the development of anxiety in them. For this the data were collected through their own opinions in the personal data blank. The result revealed that there existed family disturbances in the lives of the women teachers. So it might have put tremendous pressure on the mental aspects at home and in school. Elder people and in laws demand for sacrifice from women teachers, unruly children and siblings, property disturbances might have affected the mentality. Therefore, the investigator thought of finding out association between the anxiety levels of women teachers and their family disturbances. It was observed that the calculated chi square value of 24.01 is much greater than the table value of 13.277 to be significant at 0.01 level of significance for 4 degrees of freedom. As the chi square was significant the null hypothesis formulated in this context was rejected. This meant that there is significant association between the levels of anxiety of women teachers and their family disturbances.

Association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the adjustment of the children both boys and girls of the working women teachers.

One of the important objectives of the study was to study the association between the levels of anxiety of women teachers and its impact on the level of adjustment of secondary school children. Hence the null hypothesis H_0 was formulated as, there is no significant relation between the anxiety of women teachers and its impact on the adjustment of the secondary school children. For this the level of anxiety of women teachers were categorized under three levels like high, average and low. The corresponding level of adjustment of secondary school children was also classified under high,

average and low. They were categorized into three categories such as High, Average and Low. The scores on Adjustment scale were also tabulated and mean and SD were calculated for categorizing students under High Adjustment the cut of mark was selected at Q3 and Low adjustment at Q1 point. In between Q1 and Q3 the no. of students falling was required as students having Average level of Adjustment. The mean scores and SD were also calculated which have been presented in chapter 4. Therefore, in order to find out significant difference if any, in the Adjustment level of the students the Chi-square was calculated component wise and totally and the calculated chi-square value was found to be 7.25. But in order to be significant chi-square value for four degrees of freedom requires the table value of 9.488 at 0.05 degrees of freedom and 13.277 at 0.01 level of significance. The calculated value being 7.25 is less than the table value. Therefore, it was not significant. Hence, the null hypotheses that there is no significant relation between the levels of anxiety of women teachers with the social adjustment of the children of the working mother teachers was accepted.

Association between levels of anxiety of women teachers with emotional adjustment of the total sample.

The adjustment inventory had three components-social, emotional and educational. Therefore it was decide to find out whether any significant relationship existed between levels of anxiety of women teachers and their emotional adjustment it was observed that the chi-square test of independence was significant at 0.05 levels Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the levels of anxiety of women teachers and the emotional adjustment of their school children were rejected. This revealed that there was a significant impact of anxiety of women teachers on the emotional adjustment of their own children.

Association between anxiety level of women teachers and educational adjustment of secondary school students.

In this case, as the chi square was significant, the null hypothesis formulated in this context, that there is no significant association of women teachers and the educational adjustment of secondary school children was rejected.

Anxiety level of women teachers and level of social adjustment of boys.

The chi square calculated to study the association between the level of anxiety of the working women teachers and the social, emotional and educational adjustment of their own boy children, it was observed that in case of all the components, there could be established significant association

1. One of the major findings of the study was that the women teachers had developed anxiety due to certain socio- demographic variables. Only there was no significant impact of anxiety level of women teachers on the job satisfaction of teachers. Majority of women teachers displayed average level of anxiety. Therefore, it is concluded that the average level of anxiety of women teachers is conducive for the benefit of the school to some extent.
2. As the socio- demographic variables affected the women teachers in generating anxiety, it is concluded that family financial status, family disturbance, age, experience and educational qualification should be as per the requirement of the school.
3. The study also revealed that there is no significant association between the problems as consequences of job or any other household problem of the women teachers. Hence the conclusion is drawn that the women teachers' anxiety level was conducive for accepting the teaching job as a profession.
4. So far as the impact of anxiety level in women teachers in the level of adjustment of their children are concerned ,it was observed that in all the three components of adjustment , there was no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers on their level of social and emotional adjustment but in educational adjustment it was significant. Even though the children of working mothers did not fall in the positive group of adjustment, they also did not fall in the group of showing maladjustment problems. Hence, it is concluded that to a certain extent, the average level of anxiety in women teachers revealed normally adjusted behavior in secondary school students and very good effect on the educational adjustment, which is indispensable for the schooling system.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of the study the following recommendations are made.

1. The institutions should take necessary steps for bringing down the anxiety level of women teachers to average level by making the organizational climate joyous, so that the teachers would do better performance in the institution. This relates to the organizational effectiveness aspect of the institutions.
2. Salary to the teachers is to be paid in commensurate with the educational qualification of the women teachers so as to reduce the mental tension and frustrations in women teachers due to financial stringencies as financial status is observed to be an important factor for

between them as the chi-square values were non-significant being 3.182, 3.75 and 2.65 respectively for social, emotional and educational adjustment components.

Association between level of anxiety of women teachers and the social adjustment of girls.

The association between the mother's anxiety and social adjustment of girls the calculated chi-square value being 2.674 is much less than the table value of 9.488 at 0.05 level of significance for $df=4$. It was therefore concluded that the divergence between the expected and the observed frequencies did not yield significant result. Therefore the anxiety level of women teachers there not significantly related with the level of social adjustment of girls.

There is no significant association between the anxiety level of women teachers and the emotional adjustment of boys.

Association between level of anxiety of women teachers and the emotional adjustment of girls was also studied. The chi-square being 5.885 is also not significant indicating thereby that there is no significant relationship between the anxiety level of women teachers and the emotional adjustment of secondary school girls

Association between level of anxiety of women teachers and the educational adjustment of girls.

When the level of anxiety of women teachers were correlated with the educational adjustment of their girl children it was observed that the chi-square value was found significant being 13.56 against the table value of 9.488 at 0.05 level of significance for $df=4$. This revealed that the anxiety level of women teachers influenced their girl children in educational adjustment.

Sex differences in the levels of adjustment of the boy and girl children of the working women teachers' component wise.

The Adjustment scores of both Boys and Girls were also considered in terms of number of persons coming under high, average and low level of adjustment. The number of boys and girls in each category were calculated and the chi-square test of independence was calculated in order verify whether the level of adjustment is independent of sex. The results obtained were found to be 3.4, 4.8, and 2.72 for social, emotional and educational adjustment respectively. As none of the chi-square values were observed to be significant, it was concluded that the level of adjustment of children of working women teachers was independent of sex.

Conclusions

developing anxiety in women teachers.

3. The members of the family are to look for the comfort and peaceful co-existence in order to avoid tension and turmoil in the family life of the women teachers.

4. Excessive pressure should not be imposed on the women teachers by assigning them some outdoor activities where they will be deprived of restoring their family happiness. This will help reduce the pressure on them due to consequences in job situations.

5. There should be provisions in schools for development of rapport between the members of the staff, authority and management.

6. The parents are to take required steps for better educational improvements in their boy children.

Scope for Further Research

In a limited time frame, the study has been delimited to many factors. Any investigation undertaken by any researcher in the field of educational research is delimited to certain variables. It may not be complete in itself as it is limited to certain variables under the scope of the study. Hence, there is a need for suggesting other aspects related to it under the scope of further research.

1. A study may be conducted on male teachers of similar type taking the same variable in schools under different Boards of Examinations for wider implementation..

2. A comparative analysis of the same study may be under taken by taking both male and female teachers.

3. Another study may be undertaken to make a comparative analysis between the anxiety levels of male and female teachers and its impact upon the academic achievement of their own children.

4. A study may be conducted to investigate into the effect of socio economic status on the personality and adjustment of school going children.

References

Deb, S. and Walsh, K.(2010). Anxiety among high school students in India. *Australian Journal and Development Psychology*. Vol 10, 18-31.

Desmukh, N.H.(2004). Comparative Study of the Self-concept and Anxiety of the Athletes and Non-athletes.

Journal of Psychological Research, Vol.48(2), 88-90.

Devi,P.T.(2004). Anxiety Level among College going students. *Journal of Educational Research and Extension*, Vol41(4), 19-27.

Laskar, Z.H. (2008). *Anxiety among to Higher Secondary School students in relation to their Sex, Socio-Economic status and Self concept*. Unpublished M.Phil. Thesis in Education, Vinayaka Mission University, Salem, Tamil Nadu.

Lepcha ,K.P. (2010). *Manifest Anxiety of Higher Secondary School Students in relation to Parental Occupation and Income level*. Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis, Sikkim (Central) University, Sikkim.

Sahoo, M (2007). *Anxiety and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary students in relation to sex, Academic stream and socio-economic status*. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis, North Bengal University, Darjeeling.

Syokwaa and Aloka Ndunge(2014). Academic Achievement of children in relation to Anxiety of mothers. *Kenyan Journal of Social Science*. Retrieved from [http//www. Google.com](http://www.Google.com)

Book Review

*Dr. Pragyan Mohanty**

Title of the book: **Research Methodology Methods and Techniques Second Revised Edition**

Author's Name: **C.R. Kothari**

Publisher and Place of Publication: **New Age International Publishers, New Delhi, 110002**

Series/Volume/Edition: **Second Revised First in 1986, second 2004**

ISBN Number: **(13) 978-81-224-1522-3**

Price: ₹ **200.00**

Printed at: **Dharmesh Art Process, Delhi**

Size and Binding: **Soft Bound with a Cover leaf**

Pages: **401**

Introduction

The author Dr C.R. Kothari, Former Principal College of Commerce, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur Rajasthan, India of the Book entitled “Research Methodology: and Techniques, and revised edition has dedicated his book in the loving memory of his revered father whom he considered the fountain of Inspiration in his Preface to the Second Edition, while acknowledging gratification for enhancement of further usefulness of the book. The highlights of the revised edition of the book are as:

- Addition of a new chapter, “The Computer and its role in Research”.
- Development of the subject contents. Refinement and restructure at several points.
- Addition of New problems at the end of every chapter for the benefit of students.
- Qualitative improvement.

The book contains 15 chapters with heading and subheadings arranged hierarchically looking at the planning and development, significance of research in quality. The book is an essential document for those concerned with research with two clear cut objectives.

1. To enable researchers, irrespective of their discipline in developing the most appropriate methodology for their research studies.
2. To make them familiar with the act of using different research methods and techniques.

*Assistant Professor in Education, El-Bethel College Rasapunja, Kolkata-700104 Email-pragyan70@yahoo.co.in

Organization of the Book

The book consists of 15 chapters well arranged in a coherent manner. The print is legible, printed in 12 point font format having spacing, with soft cover page and back page. Pictorial presentation of tables and figures magnify the facial appearance of the book. All the figures are coloured and self explanatory with a clear mention of the caption and abbreviations. The book has a good approach in presentation of the contents. Each chapter has been well explained with work exercises and the relevant questions at the end of each. There are many questions also for helping students to practice. Selected References and Recommended Readings are given at the end.

Text

There are 15 chapters in all, well arranged in a coherent manner, Chapter 1 is dealt with, Research Methodology: An Introduction, where the author has clearly elucidated the Meaning and Objectives of research; citing definitions by different authors with clear cut reference given in the form of foot note. Motivation for conducting research with all its types and approaches is the most important aspect. This has been a very clear and concise attempt to differentiate between research methods and methodology procedure. It also deals with the scientific method of inquiry and importance of knowing how research is done. The different criteria of good research, research process and problems encountered in India for conduct of research are the other texts incorporated in this chapter.

Chapter 2 explains the techniques of defining a research problem where the necessity has been described along with the techniques involved and an illustrative example of the same has been presented for a clear group of the students.

Chapter 3 is devoted to different Research Designs will illustrative examples and features of a good design. The main characteristics of various designs have been highlighted with illustrative examples. As designs are of higher importance, the author has given a suitable example of how to develop a research plan.

Chapter 4 deals with the sampling design containing elements of census, survey and design. The steps for sampling design are worth mentioning.

Chapter 5, in this, the author has dealt with different measurement and scaling techniques.

Chapter 6 is dealt with the different methods of data collection. Almost all the methods have been described. Moreover a clear cut distinctive difference between questionnaires, schedules and other techniques have been described. The attempts to provide guidelines for constructing tools are a very

good attempt by the author.

Chapter 7 deals with the processing and analysis of data. Here the author has described how to apply descriptive and inferential statistics for interpretation of research data. The statistical measures have been very well exemplified and detailed work out procedure has been narrated. In an Appendix, an example thereof has also been presented for the students to learn.

Chapter 8 deals with sampling fundamentals with theory of estimation.

Chapter 9 and 10 are exclusively devoted to statistical measures with problems and examples are worked out with solutions of parametric data analysis and non-parametric measures.

The inclusion of statistical analysis in the book gives a very good picture of content and analysis of research problem. The statistical computation procedure along with the hypotheses testing are highly attractive as everything has been presented very nicely with illustrative diagrams. There has been a flow diagram for hypothesis testing which is rare to be found in other Indian Text Book. Sufficient problems have been worked out by presenting illustrations both numerically and graphically. The non-parametric tests have been presented in terms of chi-square only. But other non-parametric tests have been ignored.

Chapter 11 is concerned with ANOVA and ANCOVA. The meaning, basic principles, techniques have been well explained.

Chapter 12 is devoted towards important non-parametric tests generally used in research as techniques of hypothesis testing.

The multivariate analysis presented in Chapter 13 is highly beneficial to researchers as multivariate analysis techniques along with factor analysis procedure have been presented.

Chapter 14 presents an explicit explanation of reporting research.

The book has added a chapter in 2nd edition in the name of "The Computer and its Role in Research". In this chapter the writer has explained the need of computer technology and its application in the field of research. Any student of research must be well acquainted with the computer system. In this respect the author is praise worthy for helping researchers with advanced knowledge of computer technology.

Towards the last, the author has presented selected references, author and subject indexes along with selected statistical tables.

The book is quite necessary for any student pursuing research in Behavioral Sciences.

Acknowledgement

We extend our hearty gratitude to the following eminent educationists for taking pain in reviewing the articles published in this journal.

- 1 . Prof(Dr.) N. Pradhan , Principal, Regional Institute of Education, Bhopal
- 2 . Dr. O. P. Gadde, Asst. Professor, Dept of Pol Sc.; Sikkim University, Gangtok.
3. Dr. H. P. Mishra, Principal; Sagardighi Teachers' Training College, Murshidabad. W.B
- 4 . Dr. Sambit Kumar Padhi; Asst. Professor; Deptt. of Education, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur, Chhatisgarh.
5. Dr. P. K. Mishra; Principal, Damber Singh College; Samdur, Gangtok.
- 6 . Prof. P. L. Mohapatra; Principal, Harkamaya College of Education; Gngtok.
7. Mrs. Devikala; Asst. Professor in Education; Harkamaya College of Education, Samdur, Gangtok.
8. Ms. Ranita Chakraborty; Asst. Prof. in Education; Harkamaya College of Education; Samdur, Gangtok.
9. Ms. Magdolyn Karthak; Asst. Prof. in Education; Harkamaya College of Education; Samdur, Gangtok.

AUTHOR'S GUIDELINES

Submission of manuscript for **HIMALAYAN JOURNAL ON SOCIAL SCIENCES** should be the original work of the author(s). Author(s) is/ are transferring the copyright of the manuscript to the publisher for publishing in the journal. The publisher holds copyrights of the manuscript unless otherwise not communicated. It further implies that the manuscript has neither published anywhere nor been kept under consideration for publication.

Submitted manuscripts in English should be up to about 3500 words including Abstract, tables and references. An Abstract of 100-120 words, keywords a brief description about themselves along with areas of their specialization may be submitted along with the manuscript. The manuscript should be submitted as a Microsoft Word file in Times New Roman (12 font size) with 1.5 spacing. Two copies of the manuscripts, typed in one side of the sheet along with soft copy should be addressed to the Editor, **HIMALAYAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES**, Harkamaya College of Education, SAMDUR, P.O. Tadong, Gangtok, Sikkim- 737102

There should not be end notes/ footnotes. Authors are encouraged to send Electronic copy e-mail to plmohapatra@rediffmail.com / devilama@gmail.com / hjss.editor@rediffmail.com .

The journal reviews educational publications other than text books. Authors/ Publishers may send a copy of their latest publication for book review. The author should provide the list of references at the end of the paper in sequence as per the guidelines and the examples suggested contained in APA referencing style (6th edition).

1. **Books** : Surname followed by initials (Year). Title of the book in bold italics. Place of publication: Name of the Publisher, .pp. (referred pages).
2. **For a Paper/ Chapter in a book (multi-authored)** : Surname followed by initials (Year). Title of the paper/ chapter in bold. In title of the book in italics. pp. 45-50, edited by X and Y. place of publication: name of publisher, (Number of Pages of the book) p.
3. **Journals/Magazines/ News letter** : Surname followed by initials (Year). Title of the paper in bold. In title of the Journals/Magazines/ Newsletters in italics, Vol. No(issue No.), pp. 25-32
4. **Reports** : Surname followed by initials/organizations. (Year). Title of the report in bold (only the first letter in caps). Place of publication: Name of the Organization/ publisher, pp. (referred page numbers).

